

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium
California State University, Fullerton

Delirium and Its Sequelae in Hospitalized Older Adults Admitted from the Emergency
Department to Inpatient Units

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Linda Ruhi Mahjoub

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Roxanne O'Brien, PhD, RN, Project Chair
Dana N. Rutledge, PhD, RN, Committee Member

May 2019

Copyright Linda Ruhi Mahjoub 2019 ©

ABSTRACT

Objective: The purpose of this study was to report the incidence of delirium and its association with length of stay (LOS), discharge destination, and functional level at the time of discharge among hospitalized older patients 65 years and older who were admitted to non-intensive care units (non-ICU) through the emergency department (ED). A further aim was to describe associations between unrecognized delirium and the use of sitters, restraints, and nurse observed delirium.

Method: A prospective cohort study was conducted from September to November 2018 in a 500-bed community hospital located in southern California. The Confusion Assessment Method (CAM-ICU) and the cognition assessment test, Month of The Year Backward (MOTYB), were used to evaluate the cognitive state of the patients. Evaluation was initiated in the ED or within the first 12 hours of admission to non-ICU floors and continued for three consecutive days during patients' hospital stay. Patients were identified as delirium positive if they were assessed using the CAM-ICU to be positive on any day of assessment. Patient functional levels were measured using the Katz Activities of Daily Living (Katz ADL). Patient LOS, discharge destination, use of sitters and restraints, and nurse observed delirium were collected from the electronic medical record.

Findings: Out of 430 eligible patients, 204 consented to participate. Among participants, 146 (76.6%) had negative delirium assessment (never assessed as delirium positive), and 55 (27%) patients had at least one incident of delirium. The LOS ($p =$

.003), discharge destination ($p = .002$), and functional level ($p < .0001$) had significant associations with delirium incidence. There were also significant relationships between delirium incidence with age ($p = .039$), altered level of consciousness (LOC) at home ($p < .0001$), the use of sitters ($p = .018$), and the use of restraints ($p < .0001$). Nurses in non-ICU units documented the change of mental status or confusion in 12 (5.9%) patients out of 55 who were delirium positive, $Phi (\varphi) = .318, p < .0001$.

Conclusions: Delirium occurs in the hospital setting; its management is costly, and long-term consequences may be irreversible. Developing a multidisciplinary delirium management program that includes screening in the emergency department and non-ICU units may be useful in helping organizations to manage delirium proactively.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	ix
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	3
Local Context.....	4
Purpose Statement.....	4
Study Questions	5
Study Impact.....	5
Supporting Framework	5
Key Indicators: Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practice.....	7
Use of KAP-O in This Project.....	8
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	10
Overview.....	10
Delirium: Definition and Neuropathophysiology	13
Delirium Definition.....	13
Neuropathophysiology.....	14
Delirium Screening Tools.....	15
Delirium Screening Studies	18
Staff Knowledge	20
Delirium Prevention Programs	23
Theoretical Framework: KAP-O	25
Summary.....	26
METHODS	28
Ethical Considerations	28
Study Design, Sample, and Setting.....	29
Measures	29
Attention	30

Delirium Screening	30
Documentation of Delirium	31
Functional Level	32
Comorbidity Index	32
Other Measures	32
Data Collection	33
Data Analysis.....	33
RESULTS	35
DISCUSSION.....	45
Factors Associated with Delirium.....	45
Delirium Recognition	47
Limitations.....	49
Conclusions.....	49
REFERENCES	51
APPENDIX A: LIST OF VARIABLES USED IN THE STUDY	65
APPENDIX B: TABLE OF DELIRIUM SCREENING TOOLS	66
APPENDIX C: TABLE OF DELIRIUM SCREENING STUDIES.....	74
APPENDIX D: TABLE OF STAFF KNOWLEDGE	79
APPENDIX E: TABLE OF DELIRIUM MANAGEMENT PROGRAM.....	84
APPENDIX F: TABLE OF FRAMEWORK	92
APPENDIX G: ASSESSMENT TOOLS: KATZ ADLS	94
APPENDIX H: CHARLSON COMORBIDITY INDEX.....	95
APPENDIX I: CAM-ICU	96
APPENDIX J: THE RICHMOND AGITATION.....	97
SEDATION SCALE (RASS)	
APPENDIX K: ASSESSMENT OF CONSCIOUSNESS.....	98
APPENDIX L: CAM-ICU WORKSHEET	99
APPENDIX M: HOSPITAL CONFIRMATION LETTER	100

APPENDIX N: CERTIFICATION OF ST. JOSEPH IRB.....	101
DETERMINATION	
APPENDIX O: INFORMED CONSENT FORM.....	102

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Initial Search Strategies	12
2. Illustration of the Study Method.....	30
3. Demographic Data and Clinical Findings of Patients with and without Delirium.....	38
4. Cognitive Tests Over Three Days.....	40
5. Functional Status from Baseline through Day 3	41
6. Associations between Delirium and Functional Status Across Three Days and Length of Stay.....	42
7. Association Between Delirium and Disposition for Patients who Enter Hospital from Home	43
8. Logistic Regression Analysis for Pre-Hospital Patient Characteristics.....	44

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Conceptual Model KAP-O.....	9
2. Flowchart of Sampling.....	36
3. Nurse Observation of Positive Delirium.....	39
4. The Mean Functional Level for all Patients from Baseline to Day3	41

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

My greatest love and appreciation to my family, my dear husband and my two lovely children who lived through all excitements of my journey; I am blessed with their unconditional love and support.

I want to thank my parents for kindling my path toward knowledge and education throughout my life.

I would like to express my gratitude to my chair, Dr. O'Brien for her guidance and continuous support during this journey. Her word of wisdom and encouragement guided me at the time of great exhaustion and uncertainty.

I express my great appreciation to my team member, Dr. Rutledge for dedicating her free time to participate and support me in this project. At the time that I greatly needed faculty support to conduct this project, she supported and guided me through.

I also would like to thank Dr. Weismuller, the director of the DNP program for providing a friendly environment that promotes learning.

A sincere thanks to my friends in cohort 6; we helped each other, and we grew and flourished together through this program.

I express my appreciation to Dr. Drake and the research team at my hospital for their dedication and help during the data collection process.

My journey was a fulfilling and evolving journey. I would not be able to reach my goals without your help and support. Thank you all.

BACKGROUND

Delirium, an acute and transient confused state, is often a complication of acute illnesses and is frequent in older adults (Godfrey et al., 2013). Hospitalized older adults, especially those who take many medications and have multiple chronic conditions, are susceptible to functional and cognitive decline (Godfrey et al., 2013; Inouye, Bogardus, Baker, Leo-Summers, & Cooney, 2000). This vulnerable population accounts for 11% to 42% of delirium experiences in the hospital setting (Rosenbloom-Brunton, Henneman, & Inouye, 2010; Siddiqi et al., 2016).

Delirium is preventable when detected early and when strategies are available to manage it (Inouye et al., 2000). Studies emphasize the role of hospital nurses in delirium prevention through early identification and management (Godfrey et al., 2013; Siddiqi, Stockdale, Britton, & Holmes, 2007). Several screening tools assist with recognizing delirium among hospitalized patients (De Marchis et al., 2010; Malik, Harlan, & Cobb, 2016; Sullivan, Regan, & Timmons, 2016). Study findings support the importance of early detection and screening of at-risk patients upon entry into Emergency Departments (ED) (Han et al., 2013; Hsieh, Madahar, Hope, Zapata, & Gong, 2015).

The importance of delirium management and the consequences of unrecognized delirium have been discussed (Inouye, Bogardus, Baker, Leo-Summers, & Cooney, 2000). However, delirium recognition and management continue to be a challenge in many healthcare settings, and few hospitals have adopted delirium recognition and management programs (Harrison, 2017; Inouye, Bogardus, Baker, Leo-Summers, et al., 2000; Inouye et al., 2008; LaMantia, Messina, Hobgood, & Miller, 2014). Barriers and challenges in delirium detection and prevention are many. A major problem may be lack

of education among staff for recognizing delirium. Another is the dismissal that nursing staff can receive after reporting delirium to physicians. If reporting patient conditions to physicians does not influence the care provided to patients, nurses become discouraged to report (Steege et al., 2014). Consistency in educating and empowering nurses to implement an effective intervention to reduce delirium could encourage them to take an active role in delirium prevention and management in the hospitals.

Approximately 40% of hospitalized older patients age 70 and older can develop delirium during their hospital stay (Inouye et al., 1999). About 33% to 66% of delirium cases among non-critically ill patients go undetected (Siddiqi et al., 2007), contributing to clinical deterioration and non-anticipated admission of patients into intensive care units (ICU). Increased lengths of stay (LOS) and costs of care are consequences of undetected delirium in hospitals (Hsieh et al., 2015).

Delirium among hospitalized patients can independently predict 6-month mortality and increased costs of care (Han et al., 2011). The Medicare cost for delirium in 2011 among hospitalized patients was reported as \$11 billion a year. Post-hospitalization Medicare costs were about \$153 billion a year, resulting from costs associated with rehospitalization, emergency room visits, and rehabilitation (Leslie & Inouye, 2011).

Most delirium occurs in the first 24 hours of hospitalization (Mariz et al., 2013). Unfortunately, early delirium can persist throughout hospitalization. As documented by Hsieh et al. in a prospective study (2015), delirium persisted in 75% of cases from ED through inpatient stays. When ED physicians failed to document delirium, hospitalists failed to identify it in 99% of cases (Han et al., 2009). If delirium lasted for three days, patients were more likely to show functional and cognitive decline at the time of

discharge (Han et al., 2009). Authors of this study concluded that the absence of routine delirium screening in older adults is a major cause of under-recognized delirium (Han et al., 2009).

Problem Statement

Authors of the National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE) delirium guideline recommend screening all hospitalized patients age 65 and older for risk of cognitive disorder (Young, Murthy, Westby, Akunne, & O'Mahony, 2010). They advise using a multidisciplinary team that is trained and competent to take care of at-risk patients. Also, they recommend that nurses perform daily screening and reporting of cognitive changes to care providers (Young et al., 2010).

Early mobilization is a key delirium prevention intervention (Inouye et al., 1999). In a systemic review, Baczynska et al. (2016) evaluated programs that include early mobilization of inpatients using volunteers and noted the frequent citing of elements in the Hospital Elder Life Program (HELP). Rubin et al. (2006) implemented HELP in a community hospital, which resulted in a 14.4% absolute reduction in the delirium rate (equal to a relative reduction risk of 35.5%, $p = .002$). The total cost of care in the 40-bed unit was reduced about \$626,261 in one year (Rubin et al., 2006).

Many programs have been developed to assist with delirium prevention. However, before initiating any delirium management program, there are two key elements required in delirium recognition: (a) use of a validated tool to identify delirium, and (b) trained staff who are capable of screening patients and initiating prevention plans. To implement these elements, the awareness and support of hospital administration are essential (Young et al., 2010). Although preventing delirium would be facilitated through

prevention programs and staff education, the costs of initiating prevention programs has been reported as a barrier (Godfrey et al., 2013; Rubin, Bellon, Bilderback, Urda, & Inouye, 2018).

Local Context

A 500-bed Magnet-accredited, faith-based community hospital in southern California had 14,250 emergency visits for patients 65 years and older during 2017. Of these patients, 44.9% were admitted into non-ICU units with an average LOS of three days. During hospitalization, about 3% of these patients were restrained, and 2% who had sitters were subsequently transferred to Intensive Care Units (ICU). Since delirium assessment is not a routine practice outside the ICU in this hospital, the incidence of delirium in patients who were transferred to ICU or were restrained or had a sitter was not clear. With no local data available to identify non-critical care delirium incidence rates, the consequences of delirium are likely unrecognized. Currently, staff competency in recognizing delirium has not been evaluated, and delirium screening and prevention have not been integrated in current practice.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice study was to assess, analyze, and report on the incidence of delirium and its association with the length of stay (LOS), discharge destination, and patients' functional level at the time of discharge among hospitalized older patients who were admitted to non-ICU units through the Emergency Department (ED). Another study aims was to analyze the associations between unrecognized delirium and the use of sitters, restraints, falls and nurse observed and reported cases of delirium.

Study Questions

The primary question was:

- What is the incidence of delirium (recognized and unrecognized) in patients 65 years and older during the first three days of hospitalization?

Additional questions were:

- What are the associations between incident delirium and the following: the length of stay (LOS), discharge destination, and functional level?
- What are the associations between incident delirium on the use of sitters, use of restraints, and nurse observed delirium?

Study Impact

Findings from this study allowed the following to occur at the hospital: (a) brought awareness about delirium and its sequelae to the attention of health care providers, and (b) identified gaps in providing care to patients with delirium due to failure to recognize delirium. These findings may lead to the development of planning and implementing multidisciplinary delirium prevention and management strategies in this hospital.

Supporting Framework

The linear framework of knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) can be considered a model for change. The knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) (sometimes called knowledge, attitude, and behavior or KAB) (Xu et al., 2010) was developed in 1950 (Rav-Marathe, Wan, & Marathe, 2016). Since 1960, it has been used in family planning and population studies in order to assess and guide programs in public health (Marias & Glasauer, 2014). Marias and Glasauer applied the KAP model to nutrition

programs. KAP can be used in any area of health programs, but its main purpose is to (a) collect information during a situation in order to use that information to design an intervention, and (b) evaluate educational interventions (Marias & Glasauer, 2014).

The KAP model assists in analyzing and evaluating situations (called situational analysis) by identifying existing knowledge, attitudes, and practices in regard to that issue, followed by using the findings to help develop an educational intervention (Marias & Glasauer, 2014). Marias and Glasauer explained that a situational analysis is different than a baseline survey. A situational analysis is performed during project planning, since it has a planning function purpose (Marias & Glasauer, 2014). Monitoring and evaluating the intervention is an essential part of this model that guarantees the project is on the right track in achieving its intended outcomes. This version of KAP includes the abbreviation 'O' for outcomes, and uses the acronym KAP-O. Assessing outcomes helps the project planner to demonstrate the finding to funding agencies and local stakeholders (Marias & Glasauer, 2014).

The outcomes can be divided into short, medium, and long-term. For example, increased knowledge regarding feeding children certain foods has the short-term outcome of changing a mother's attitude by increasing her confidence in preparing those foods (increased self-efficiency/confidence) (Marias & Glasauer, 2014). Change in nutritional practice, such as frequently preparing food for children, is an example of medium outcomes. Change in a physiological parameter, such as increasing the iron level in the blood is an example of long-term outcomes. Usually the short-term and medium-term outcomes are social, and behavioral changes and the long term outcomes are psychological (Marias & Glasauer, 2014).

Key Indicators: Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practice

Knowledge. Knowledge is awareness or understanding of any given topic (Marias & Glasauer, 2014). Knowledge can be measured by asking questions or filling out a predefined questionnaire. Predefined options in a questionnaire make the analysis easier (Marias & Glasauer, 2014). Currently, there has been no assessment of providers' knowledge about delirium at the study hospital. Providing information regarding delirium incidence may increase the understanding of the topic among medical and nursing staff and help them to become more effective at early detection of delirium.

Attitudes. Attitudes are affected by emotions, motivations, and perceptions. Cognitive acceptance can positively or negatively influence the behavior or practice of individuals (Marias & Glasauer, 2014). For example, a person's attitude towards feeding children a homemade porridge is influenced by the person's emotion, motivation, and thoughts (Marias & Glasauer, 2014). Attitudes may affect future behavior regardless of the level of the knowledge. Attitudes can help to explain why individuals adopt one practice over another. For example, increasing a mother's belief in the benefit of preparing diverse foods for her children will affect her attitude toward preparing these foods (Marias & Glasauer, 2014).

During two one-hour meetings with hospital administration in the project hospital, some barriers in the beliefs of effectiveness of a delirium intervention program were identified. Since there is no baseline data about delirium at this time, delirium is not perceived as a priority problem (lack of a potential readiness to change) (Marias & Glasauer, 2014).

Practices. Practices are defined as visible actions of individuals. Practice examples in nutrition include eating, cooking, and feeding (Marias & Glasauer, 2014). Regarding delirium, the project hospital does not have a policy for delirium screening and management, and there is no budget for educating staff about the actions to take for delirium screening and prevention in non-ICU units. Practice could be a policy for daily screening of at-risk patients and implementing a delirium education program for nurses.

As Zaccagnni and White (2017) indicated, nursing models are not abstract notions, and in the process of using the KAP model, Rav-Marathe et al. (2016) realized that measuring outcomes is an essential element when implementing the KAP model. Therefore, they added the “outcome” to the original linear KAP model and they called it (KAP-O).

Use of KAP-O in This Project

The KAP model is commonly used because it is simple to apply (Muleme, Kankya, Ssempebwa, Mazeri, & Muwonge, 2017). The KAP-O model is an appropriate model for this doctoral project because of its simplicity, logical order, and application to the issue of delirium screening by nurses and understanding hospital outcomes.

Analyzing the existing problem based on the KAP-O model revealed a current lack of knowledge about delirium incidence and its sequelae at the hospital. This affects the approaches toward prevention or management of delirium. Conducting a research study to evaluate the incidence of delirium in hospitalized older patients may bring awareness about the extent of the lack of screening processes and make changes to improve practice. If the hospital implements delirium screening and prevention, the ultimate outcome could be increased quality of care for older adults at the hospital. In this phase of project, the

focus was to measure the incidence of delirium and its outcomes for patients 65 and older who enter the hospital from the emergency department. Future application of this understanding would be expected to build a delirium prevention and management program.

This author modified the KAP-O model (Rav-Marathe et al., 2016) to address the interaction between outcomes and knowledge, attitude, and practice. Adding a relation arrow between knowledge and outcomes indicates that providers need to be aware of clinical outcomes (e.g., delirium rates and sequelae) and continually evaluate the system, identify potential barriers and apply the appropriate interventions (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Adaptation of Knowledge, Attitude, Practice and Outcome Model (KAP-O). KAP-O Model was adapted from “A *Systematic Review on the KAP-O framework for Diabetes Education and Research,*” by K. Rav-Marathe, T. Wan, S. Marathe, 2016, *Medical Research Archives*, 4(1), p. 16. Copyright 2016 by Knowledge Enterprises, Inc. Journals.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

The literature review was conducted to assess and analyze the challenges that exist in evaluating and managing delirium, as well as to explore screening instruments, and review non-pharmacological delirium management programs. The literature search was broken into the following subtopics: (a) delirium screening tools, (b) delirium screening studies, (c) staff knowledge, (d) delirium prevention programs, and (e) KAP-O Framework. A reference book was used for foundational and pathophysiological understanding of delirium in older adults. For each topic a comprehensive search was conducted using Medline/PubMed (NLM), CINAHL Plus with Full-text (EBSCO), ProQuest Medical Library, Cochrane Library (Wiley), and Google Scholar. The selection was limited to English, peer reviewed, qualitative, quantitative and systemic reviewed articles published between 2013-2018. The reference section of selected articles was reviewed, and related older articles were included.

In order to find evidence about delirium screening, online databases were searched using the following terms: (a) delirium, (b) delirium and screening, (c) delirium and early recognition, (d) delirium and hospitalized older adult, (e) hospitalized and 65 and older and delirium, (f) delirium and non-ICU (g) delirium assessment tools, (h) delirium assessment instruments, (i) delirium in emergency departments (EDs), (j) unrecognized delirium and hospital and non ICU, (k) early recognition and delirium, (l) delirium risk factors, (m) ED delirium recognition tools; and (n) validity and reliability of delirium tools. After reviewing the abstracts of selected articles and eliminating duplications and articles that did not meet the search criteria, 40 articles were selected for

full review. Among these, 14 articles discussed screening tools, and eight discussed screening studies. Those articles were used in the Tables of Evidence (TOE) (Appendix B and C).

For literature concerning staff knowledge and awareness about delirium the following keywords were used: (a) delirium, (b) delirium recognition, (c) hospitalized older patients and delirium, (d) 65 and older and delirium, (e) delirium risk factors, (f) unrecognized delirium and older hospitalized patients, (g) barriers to screen delirium, (h) barriers to detect delirium, (i) nursing knowledge and delirium, and (j) non-ICU, delirium and under-recognized. The same limits were applied to select the articles for this section (Appendix D).

The literature describing delirium prevention programs were selected by searching for (a) delirium prevention programs, (b) delirium interventions, (c) delirium prevention and volunteers, (d) non-ICU and delirium prevention, (e) delirium and outcomes, (f) non-pharmacological intervention and delirium, (g) Hospital Elder Life Program (HELP), (h) National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), hospitalized older adult and prevention and delirium, (i) older patients or 65 and older and delirium prevention, (j) delirium risk factors, unrecognized delirium and prevention, and (k) volunteer to assist and delirium. Literature in this area was vast, therefore, to eliminate the number of articles, articles on HELP, systemic review, guidelines, and volunteer assistance programs were prioritized. After reviewing the abstracts of 30 selected articles, 14 items were selected for this review (Appendix E).

Selected keywords for the theoretical framework were nursing models and nursing framework. After reading about various nursing models, the author decided to

adapt the KAP-O model. The search was then narrowed to (a) KAP-O, (b) knowledge, attitude and practice, (c) nursing and health care, (d) KAP-O and hospital care, and (e) examples of KAP in hospitals. Twenty- seven articles were found. Articles mainly focused on patient education. A systemic review article and two KAP examples were selected for the TOE (Appendix F). The summary of the total numbers of the articles on each topic, and the search terms that were used are reported in Table 1.

Table 1

Initial Search Strategy

Topic	Search Terms	Search Term Combinations	#
Delirium screening & Screening tools	Delirium recognition	Delirium, recognition, hospitalized, older patients, 65 and older, delirium risk factors Delirium, older, Emergency Early delirium screening tools, older hospitalized	133
	Delirium screening in older people	delirium outcome in hospitals Unrecognized in older hospitalized patients	35
	Delirium screening tools	Early delirium screening, tools, older patients, non-ICU delirium screening tool, ED Validity and reliability	188
Delirium prevention programs	Non-pharmacological intervention	Delirium prevention programs Interventions volunteers Non-ICU Outcomes HELP NICE	344
Framework: KAPO	Knowledge attitude practice and outcome framework	Example of KAPO in hospitals Knowledge, Attitude, practice Nursing Healthcare, framework, model	27

In the following section, the definition of delirium and its pathophysiology, and the findings of the literature review will be presented. Additional information about

delirium will be presented in following order: (a) delirium screening tools, (b) delirium screening studies, (c) staff knowledge, (d) delirium prevention programs, and (e) description of the KAP-O framework.

Delirium: Definition and Neuropathophysiology

Delirium definition and neuropathophysiology are explained in this section. In the literature review section, the latest tools used for screening delirium and their validity and reliability are discussed.

Delirium Definition

Historically, delirium has been defined as a state of acute confusion. The definition and conceptualization of delirium has been modified to describe a range of mental disorders that impairs consciousness and frequently is associated with medical illness (Lindesay, Rockwood, & Macdonald, 2002). The definition of delirium has been adjusted and altered many times. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-IV)(1994) defined delirium as a medical condition due to substance intoxication or withdrawal, or other causes such as sensory deprivation, an abrupt change in clarity and awareness of the environment especially in a patient with dementia (Lindesay et al., 2002). The DMS-V defines delirium as a disturbance in attention and cognition that develops over short periods of time (Meagher et al., 2014). The disturbance in cognition and attention is not related to preexisting or developing neurocognitive disorders, as this disturbance can be a consequence of a medical condition, substance intoxication, or multiple etiologies (Meagher et al., 2014). The International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10) does not specify the underlying medical disorders for delirium.

Neuropathophysiology

Delirium is a neurobehavioral condition in which the brain cortical function and neural circuits are affected (Maldonado, 2013). Because of its cognitive effect, delirium was initially described as a neuropsychiatric disorder caused by acute brain dysfunction (Lindesay et al., 2002). Slowness in the electroencephalogram (EEG) study results from the widespread cortical dysfunction has been observed during delirium. These changes could indicate the different symptoms of delirium. Neuroimaging of delirious patients suggests involvement of the prefrontal cortex, anterior thalamus, non-dominant parietal and fusiform cortex (Lindesay et al., 2002). There are at least seven known theories about the pathological process of delirium (Maldonado, 2013). Most of those are related to how the neurotransmitters interact and their imbalances influence cognitive and behavioral changes in delirium (Maldonado, 2013). The most commonly described neurotransmitter changes are related to acetylcholine or melatonin availability, and to the excess in dopamine, norepinephrine, and/or glutamate release. Changing levels of histamine and γ -aminobutyric acid may also contribute to delirium. Maldonado (2013) stated that no theory can fully explain the etiology of delirium, but two or more of these theories could explain the biochemical changes that lead to the behavioral and cognitive characteristics of delirium (Maldonado, 2013).

Morphological changes occur in the aging brain. Through the aging process, the volume and number of neurons decreases, and neurons lose dendrites and synapses. However, even with these changes, the human brain has a high capacity to preserve its function. Aging also affects the neurotransmitter system and its functions. The aging process causes selective cell loss in the basal forebrain, decreases synthetic choline

acetyltransferase, and decreases synthesis of acetylcholine in the hippocampal and cortical area (Lindesay et al., 2002). The deterioration of the cholinergic system may be related to memory impairment in both healthy aging and Alzheimer's disease (Lindesay et al., 2002). Serotonin metabolism also changes during aging and, in some regions of the brain, the concentration of serotonin decreases. This deficit in serotonergic function may increase the chances of delirium among older adults (Lindesay et al., 2002). Although there is no approved medication to prevent and treat delirium, the use of antipsychotics (such as haloperidol) and alpha-2 agonists (like clonidine and dexmedetomidine) are general clinical approaches (Hipp & Ely, 2012).

A combination of a cognitive assessment and delirium screening tools have been recommended to screen patients for delirium (Lindesay et al., 2002). Lindesay et al. provided an overview of the assessment tools as of the publication date in their book. Although Lindesay et al. (2002) is an older reference, their reported tools are still in use by researchers.

Delirium Screening Tools

Delirium is under-diagnosed among older hospitalized patients, 65 or older, and this has been addressed in many studies (Han et al., 2011; Hshieh, Inouye, & Oh, 2018; Inouye, Westendorp, Saczynski, Kimchi, & Cleinman, 2014; Kuczmarska et al., 2016). With the aim of helping healthcare providers to accurately and quickly assess patients for delirium, many screening tools have been developed (Appendix B). Using a cognitive assessment tool in combination with a delirium screening instrument is common practice across all studies (Fortini et al., 2014; Grossmann et al., 2014; Han, Schnelle, & Ely,

2014; Heim et al., 2015; LaMantia et al., 2014). In this section, delirium screening tools and their validity and reliability will be discussed.

Several studies in the last five years have tried to identify the strength of the tools and describe their reliability and validity in specific settings (Barron, 2013; Fortini, 2014; Han, 2011; McCrow, 2013). Among all screening tools, one of the most reliable and validated instruments is the Cognitive Assessment Method (CAM) (LaMantia, et al., 2014). The CAM has been validated and translated into many languages. It has also been modified based on the needs and characteristics of the study setting (e.g., CAM-ICU, b-CAM, m-CAM, CAM-ED: information about these tools are provided in Appendix B). The sensitivity and specificity of CAM has been reported as 94% and 89%, and sensitivity and specificity of modify CAM tools were also in the same range (Appendix B) (Barman et al., 2018; Dyer, Briggs, Nabeel, O'Neill, & Kennelly, 2017; Fortini et al., 2014; Gelinas et al., 2018; Grossmann, Hasemann, Kressig, Bingisser, & Nickel, 2017; Han et al., 2013; Hasemann et al., 2017; Kuczmarska et al., 2016; LaMantia et al., 2014).

Screening high risk patients in the ED with a reliable and quick tool has been studied in the last decade. One of the tools examined was the brief-CAM, or b-CAM (Han et al., 2013). Han et al. (2013) used the Digit Span Test (DST) and the b-CAM to screen ED patients for delirium. The specificity and sensitivity of the DST (55% & 98%) and b-CAM (84% & 95.8%) was evaluated compared to the reference tool. The specificity and sensitivity of DST and b-CAM reported for the physicians (MD) and research assistants (RA) using it were 55% and 99% (MD); 78% and 96.9% (RA). Han et al. (2013) showed that a 2-step screening (using DST and b-CAM) could be performed quickly in the ED. A systemic review of 22 studies evaluated the validity of seven

assessment tools that had been used in ED (LaMantia et al., 2014): the (a) CAM, (b) CAM-ICU, (c) CAM-ED, (d) Original Brain Syndrome Scale, (e) Delirium Rating Scale (DRS), (f) Diagnostic and Statistical Criteria, and (g) the NEECHAM confusion scale. They reported that only 2 of these studies discussed the validity of the tools for the ED; this may have affected the delirium recognition rate in ED, depending on what tool has been used (Appendix B).

Several tools have been reported to evaluate delirium in non-ICU settings. De and Wand (2015) performed a systemic review of available delirium assessment tools and found 21 validated tools. The most common were the CAM, CAM-ICU, b-CAM, DRS, and DRS-R-98 (Appendix B). They reported that CAM had good sensitivity and specificity in the ED, post-operative area, and mixed inpatient setting (CAM sensitivity and specificity > 95%). The DRS and DRS-R-98 had good sensitivity and specificity (82% & 94%) in mixed inpatient and geriatric units (De & Wand, 2015).

Some studies evaluated the inter-rater agreement between nurses and physicians, or research assistants and physicians. These findings showed a high agreement between two of the raters for the CAM. This was another advantage of the CAM compared to other screening tools (Appendix B) (Barman et al., 2018; Han et al., 2013). Another study compared a newly developed tool, 3D-CAM, to CAM-ICU for non-ICU patients (Kuczmarska et al., 2016). Sensitivity and specificity of 3D-CAM (92% & 77%) compared favorably to CAM-ICU (62% & 100%). The authors concluded 3D-CAM was easier to use and had higher sensitivity for medical units (Kuczmarska et al., 2016).

The AGS post-operative delirium guideline (2014) stated that studies evaluating the sensitivity and specificity of delirium assessment tools were insufficient. Although

more recent studies have addressed this deficit and assessed the psychometric strength of the tools, few had a strong design and data analysis. Among all studies the CAM screening tool had the best rating for sensitivity and specificity (Appendix B).

Delirium Screening Studies

Delirium has been estimated to exist among 7-10% of patients 65 years and older in EDs (Han et al., 2009). Early recognition of delirium has been reported as an essential patient outcome indicator. It affects patients' length of stay (LOS), discharge disposition, the readmission rate, hospital mortality rate, and decline in functional level at time of discharge (Fortini et al., 2014; Han et al., 2011; Han et al., 2010; Mariz et al., 2013; van Velthuijsen, Zwakhalen, Mulder, Verhey, & Kempen, 2017).

Routine screening for delirium can help with early recognition of delirium (Han et al., 2009). Specifically, screening would help with recognizing hypoactive delirium. Hypoactive delirium had high rates of under-recognition and high in-hospital mortality ($p = .012$) (van Velthuijsen et al., 2017). Unfortunately, about 76% of hypoactive delirium went undiagnosed by ED physicians (Han et al., 2009). Admitting physicians almost always (in 99% of cases) missed identifying delirium, if also missed by the ED physicians (Han et al., 2009). Having delirium screening as a standard practice could improve the efficiency of delirium identification (Han et al., 2009; Mariz et al., 2013). Han et al. (2009) suggested that the cause of underdiagnosed delirium in the ED is due to lack of routine screening assessment in ED.

Studies consistently showed that prolonged, unrecognized delirium has the worst outcomes (Appendix C). The delirium status that persisted from ED through hospitalization could cause clinical deterioration and poor patient outcomes (Hsieh et al.,

2015). In their prospective cohort study, Hsieh et al. (2015) reported that 29 (11 %) out of 260 patients had delirium in the ED. ED physicians did not identify delirium in 52% of the cases (15 patients). Among 29 patients with delirium in the ED who were admitted to the hospital, some were also screened as having delirium on the first day ($n = 9$), some during the second day ($n = 4$) and some on the third day of hospitalization ($n = 5$). Patients who had persistent delirium on all three-days of hospitalization had an increased chance of ICU admission (OR 8.07, $p = .005$). Delirium within three days did not have a significant effect on the functional decline at the time of discharge ($p = .08$); however, persistent delirium for the first three days increased functional decline at the discharge time ($p = .012$) (Hsieh et al., 2015).

Being kept for more than 12 hours in the ED before admission to an inpatient unit was a reliable indicator of delirium incidence in the hospital (Emond et al., 2017). In their retrospective cohort study, Emond et al. (2017) also found that delirious patients who stayed longer in the ED received more narcotic-based medications and increased their LOS from an average of 10.2 days to 17.9 days ($p = .05$).

Among all studies listed in screening studies (Appendix C), early recognition was defined as screening vulnerable patients (age 65 and older) for delirium in the first 24 hours of admission. Since delirium has a rapid onset and fluctuating symptoms over time, frequent screening was recommended (Han et al., 2009; Hsieh et al., 2015; Mariz et al., 2013; van Velthuisen et al., 2017). Delirium screening at a minimum of every shift was reported as critical to identifying new cases of delirium. Also, studies supported that positive screening for delirium in the ED should trigger subsequent screening for delirium (Han et al., 2009; Hsieh et al., 2015; Mariz et al., 2013; van Velthuisen et al.,

2017). Han et al. (2011) evaluated the relationship between the diagnosis of delirium in the ED with the LOS and readmission rate. Out of 628 screened patients, 17.2% ($n = 108$) had delirium while in the ED and were admitted to the hospital. The average LOS for delirious patients was four days and non-delirious patients 2.5 days ($p = .001$).

The adverse outcomes associated with failure to recognize and intervene when delirium was present during hospitalization were discussed in many studies (Han et al., 2011; Han et al., 2010; Mariz et al., 2013; van Velthuisen et al., 2017). Mariz et al. (2013) noted that 20% of patients had delirium during their hospital stay with 60% of delirium identified in the first 24-hours of admission, and 24% between the first and third day. They reported that patients with mixed delirium had longer delirium status and longer LOS ($p < .001$; $p < .009$). The mortality rate in the month after discharge for the delirium group was 30% versus 10% for non-delirium patients ($p < .001$) (Mariz et al., 2013).

Although studies showed that use of a validated standard screening method could increase detection rate of delirium, under-recognition is still a problem. With heterogeneity among screening tools used to screen patients, the maximum rate of delirium detection among physicians in the ED was 24% (Barron & Holmes, 2013). To improve delirium care and outcomes in hospitals, delirium detection should improve. Screening patients for cognitive dysfunction was identified as the first step to improve delirium detection in hospitals, especially in EDs (Barron & Holmes, 2013).

Staff Knowledge

Nurses play a significant role in recognizing delirium. Since they have 24-hour accountability for patients, recognizing cognitive fluctuation in their patients may be

more apparent for them. However, regardless of delirium severity, only a minority of nurses recognize delirium, and 30% to 70% of cases were not detected (El Hussein, Hirst, & Salyers, 2015; Godfrey et al., 2013; Inouye, Bogardus, Baker, Leo-Summers, et al., 2000; Siddiqi et al., 2016). Researchers found nurses' knowledge an important indicator in delirium recognition; also, they found adherence to delirium screening a challenge among the staff in hospital settings (see Appendix D) (El Hussein et al., 2015; Godfrey et al., 2013; Inouye, Bogardus, Baker, Leo-Summers, et al., 2000; Siddiqi et al., 2016).

The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) recommends staff education and workshops to increase staff awareness about delirium (Tauro, 2014). Findings from several studies supported that educating nurses about delirium and screening tools increases nurse awareness and accountability in managing delirium (El Hussein et al., 2015; Filinson, Clark, Burbank, & Stoukides, 2016; Malik et al., 2016; McCrow, Sullivan, & Beattie, 2013; Yanamadala, Wieland, & Heflin, 2013). Filinson et al. (2016) argued that despite the availability of delirium tools, barriers in implementation of standardized screening tools may relate to staff perceptions of the importance of delirium assessment. Nurse uncertainty about their role in delirium recognition and the concerns that physicians may discount their findings were also reported as barriers in using screening tools (Filinson et al., 2016).

El Hussein et al. (2015) looked at the reasons why delirium was not detected by nurses. They found that there was no consistency between physicians and nurses in their definition of delirium. Nurses usually do not have enough education on cognitive screening tools, and their knowledge of the importance in screening patients was identified as inadequate (El Hussein et al., 2015). Given the minimum education about

delirium in nursing schools, these authors concluded that educating nurses about delirium and screening tools would increase the delirium recognition rate.

In a qualitative study performed in the Netherlands, 63 healthcare providers, including nurses, physicians and hospital policy advisors, were interviewed to determine why delirium care guidelines had low support among nurses (Steeg, Langelaan, Ijkema, Nugus, & Wagner, 2014). Their findings showed that nurses were not interested in using another screening tool; they perceived it as another registration form that they had to fill out. Steeg et al. (2014) concluded that this demonstrates a lack of motivation. Lack of knowledge and skills were other identified problems. Nurses thought they already had enough knowledge or skills and if they saw a patient with delirium, they already knew it, and the use of a screening tool was not necessary. The third finding showed that nurses did not perceive screening for delirium as critical as their other daily duties. They did not view it as part of older adult care. Nurses reported that the first thing they omit from their daily duties, due to lack of time, was delirium screening (Steeg et al., 2014). The authors concluded that for the successful implementation of a program or a change, the rationale for change and its benefit for patients should be clearly explained through education and feedback.

Another descriptive study compared the impact of training and education between two hospitals in the U.S. (Filinson et al., 2016). Delirium screening was improved in both hospitals after training nurses. Education also had a positive effect on staff perception about delirium. This study showed that education could improve the use of screening tools among nurses that were not familiar with delirium and mental screening tools.

Education helped to reduce resistance to assessment and increased sustainability of screening (Filinson et al., 2016).

Delirium Prevention Programs

The AGS stated that implementation of non-pharmacological interventions could improve clinical outcomes for delirium (Wagner, 2015). Interventions in their clinical practice guidelines include sleep protocols, early ambulation, cognitive reorientation, physical rehabilitation, sensory enhancement, altering the physical environment, recognizing and managing underlying causes, pain management strategies, fluid intake monitoring, and nutrition management with the help of a multidisciplinary team. The focus of this literature review was only on non-pharmacological interventions of delirium management (these recommendations are listed in Appendix E).

The Hospital Elder Life Program (HELP) is a well-known program that emphasizes delirium management and prevention with volunteer assistance. This program has been implemented in more than 200 hospitals nationwide (HELP, 2017). International researchers have evaluated the benefit, sustainability, feasibility and cost of the HELP program or adaptations of the program (Baczynska et al., 2016; Bakker et al., 2014; Chong et al., 2011; Hsieh et al., 2015; Inouye, Bogardus, Baker, Leo-Summers, et al., 2000; Rice et al., 2017; Rubin et al., 2018; Rubin et al., 2006; Steunenbergh, van der Mast, Strijbos, Inouye, & Schuurmans, 2016). Rubin et al. (2018) compared the data collected from eight medical surgical units using the HELP program with 10 medical surgical units without the HELP program. Their findings indicated that HELP decreased the readmission rates by 2% compared to control units (16.9 % vs. 18.9%) which translated to 100 cases fewer readmission in a year. Although 100 less readmissions have

significant effect on hospital cost savings, the finding was not statistically significant (IRR = 0.92, 95% CI [0.81 - 1.04] $p = .16$) (Rubin et al., 2018). Rice et al. (2017) evaluated the feasibility of an adaptation of the HELP volunteer-based therapeutic activities program, a multicomponent program on a stroke unit (See Appendix E). Their findings indicated that adaptation of the program was feasible and did not interfere with routine stroke care (Rice et al., 2017; Rubin, Bellon, Bilderback, Urda, & Inouye, 2017).

The Care Well Hospital program (CWH) is a geriatric program that uses a combination of geriatric nursing team, HELP, and volunteer programs to improve hospitalized older adult care in the hospital. Pre and post study of the program implementation did not show any significant differences in decreasing the incidence of delirium across units in a university-based hospital in the Netherlands ($p = .945$) (Bakker et al., 2014). The researchers discussed that this finding might be related to the low delirium rate and high comorbidity rate at the baseline measurement, and the timing of the study (Bakker et al., 2014). They emphasized that even though their finding was not statistically significant due to the timing of the study (a newly implemented program and ongoing learning curve) and limitation in the design, the CWH revealed improved patient cognition at the time of discharge and return of ADLs in three months to post-surgery functional level. Also, care giver burden was reported lower in an informal evaluation (Bakker et al., 2014).

NICE provided a comprehensive guideline on how to recognize and treat delirium (Young et al., 2010). The NICE recommendations for delirium management are very similar to HELP with three additional care areas: hypoxia, infection, and pain (Yue et al., 2014). The focus on infection emphasized better hand hygiene, and prevention strategies

for aspiration pneumonia and catheter associated urinary tract infection (Yue et al., 2014). Yue et al. (2014) developed their protocol based on NICE and HELP, adding constipation management. Their aim was to update the existing guidelines to be applicable to broader range of practice (Yue et al., 2014). This protocol has been evaluated by experts (Yue et al., 2014).

Different delirium prevention programs were identified through the literature review. Although the programs may have different names, they are mainly adaptations of the HELP or NICE programs (Appendix E: Delirium management programs).

Theoretical Framework: KAP-O

The knowledge, attitude, practice, and outcomes (KAP-O) approach is a very practical model that is commonly seen in the patient education literature. The main emphasis of this framework is to consider the effect of knowledge on changes in behavior (Xu et al., 2010). Since 1960, the KAP model has been mainly used in family planning studies (Jaccard, Helbig, Wan, Gutman, & Kritz-Silverstein, 1996), and it has been reported to be cost-effective (Rav-Marathe et al., 2016). The KAP model has been used in framing health policy changes addressing human behavior in relation to public health issues (Rav-Marathe et al., 2016). Most evaluations using the KAP model have been non-experimental.

In a cross-sectional, community-based study in Uganda, the relationship between knowledge, attitude, and practice was evaluated (Muleme et al., 2017). The findings showed that knowledge and attitude had a more linear relationship than knowledge and practice. The correlation between knowledge and attitude was high (CI = 0.76 [69 - .81] $p = 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$), but the correlation was much less for knowledge and practice (CI = .32 [.18 -

.45] $p = 1.87 \text{ e-}05$) (Appendix F: Framework, KAP-O). Many socio-behavioral variables may have affected on how attitude may play a role in regard to knowledge (Muleme et al., 2017).

In a tertiary hospital setting in India, the KAP model was used to frame the implementation of a hand hygiene program (Rynga, Kumar, Gaind, & Rai, 2017). Even though self-reported evaluation by staff showed that they knew about hand hygiene, there was a gap in hand hygiene practices. Using the KAP model helped to identify the gaps and allowed interventions to occur.

Summary

To accurately evaluate delirium, reliable tools, accountable and educated staff and medical personnel are needed. Many tools have been used to screen patients for delirium in different settings. The findings of this review showed that the most commonly used and psychometrically sound tool to evaluate delirium in non-critical care areas and EDs was the CAM. There are several modified versions of CAM (see Appendixes B & C for a listing of versions of CAM). Among them CAM-ICU had been used in many different settings and has high validity and reliability (Appendix B) (Mariz et al., 2013). Also, delirium screening studies showed that there is a high inter-rater reliability among trained RAs and physicians when using CAM. Studies did not show significant differences in the results for the type of cognitive evaluation tools used in combination with CAM.

Besides demographic data, many studies evaluated the covariables in relation to delirium to assess the outcome of delirium incidence. Among those, the Charlson comorbidity index and Katz ADLs were used the most (Appendix C). The most frequently measured outcome metrics for delirium sequelae were transfer to a higher

level of care, LOS, function level at discharge, and discharge destination. The KAP-O model may be useful in explaining the impact of increasing awareness about delirium and its influence on clinicians' attitudes towards a delirium prevention program. The best results of staff education related to delirium screening and treatment were observed when the education was interactive, reinforced, and feedback was collected from staff (Yanamadala et al., 2013).

In the study hospital, delirium screening is not part of daily practice outside the ICU. There is no regular reporting of the incidence of delirium and no plan has been initiated to prevent delirium outside the ICU. This literature review helped to identify potential screening tools, outcome metrics, and methods that could be used to understand the incidence of delirium in this hospital. The findings of this study showed delirium is under-recognized in the project setting, a second and third phase of the project is recommended for improvement of the care provided to older adult in the project hospital. These steps include delirium education for staff, and implementation of a hospital-wide delirium prevention and management program.

METHODS

In this prospective cohort study, eligible patients entering the hospital from the ED were assessed for 3-days to measure the incidence of delirium when admitted to non-ICU units. Associations between delirium incidence and the following outcomes were evaluated: (a) patients' length of stay (LOS), (b) level of functioning over the three days of assessment and at the time of discharge, and (c) discharge destination. Also, the association between incident delirium and the use of sitters or restraints, falls, and nursing documentations of observed and reported delirium were analyzed. The findings of this study will assist in identifying an opportunity for improving identification of delirium, the care of these patients, and may clarify the need for initiating a delirium prevention program. This study is a partial replication of an earlier study on incidence and prevalence of delirium (Hsieh et al., 2015).

Ethical Considerations

The project protocol was approved by the hospital system and the California State University Fullerton institutional review boards (Appendix N). The information about the study was presented on a written informed consent form (Appendix O). Written consent was obtained from all patients before registering them for the study. The investigator spent 5-10 minutes explaining the protocol and the appropriate essential information to the patients or surrogate decision maker before obtaining informed consent. If the patient was delirious and there was no surrogate at the bedside, the patient was excluded from enrollment. The patient or surrogate received a copy of the signed informed consent form.

Study Design, Sample, and Setting

This prospective cohort study was conducted from September to November 2018 in a 500-bed community hospital located in southern California. The ED in this hospital has an average of 14,000 older adult patient (age 65 and older) visits per year. The author (also the primary investigator or PI) screened eligible ED patients during various hours throughout the day dependent on her availability. Patients were eligible for study participation if they were 65 years and older, were listed or admitted to a non-ICU unit from the ED, spoke English, and gave written consent to participate. Excluded were ED patients who were planned critical care admissions, non-English speaking, confused with no surrogate at the bedside, acutely aphasic, or comatose. Also excluded were those with previous diagnosis of dementia or alcohol intoxication, or those taking medications that may cause delirium such as benzodiazepines, narcotics, and antipsychotics.

Measures

The PI, who is an RN, performed all assessments. These included delirium screenings, assessments of patient cognition, functional level, and Charlson comorbidities index. Discharge destination, falls (before hospitalization or during hospitalization), use of restraints or sitters, medical diagnosis, and nursing documentation on observed and reported delirium collected from the medical record. The assessments were initiated in the ED or within the first 12 hours of admission and continued for three consecutive days from admission. Patients' age, gender, and living status (e.g., home or skilled nursing facility; other living arrangements such as board and care and assisted living facility were coded as home) were collected at baseline. The list of variables measured in this study is

illustrated in Appendix A. Table 2 illustrates the data collection measures and the tools that were used.

Table 2.

Illustration of Study Measures

Day 1 (ED/first 12 hours of admission)	Day 2	Day 3	Chart review at time of admission (A) or discharge (D)
			Age, Gender, Living status (A)
			Medical Diagnosis (D)
MOTYB	MOTYB	MOTYB	Past medical History (A)
CAM-ICU	CAM-ICU	CAM-ICU	Discharge destination (H, NH, ICU, EX, OH)
Katz ADLs	Katz ADLs	Katz ADLs	Restraints (yes/no) (D)
Charlson Comorbidity Index			Fall (yes/no) (D)
			Sitter (yes/no) (D)
			LOS (D)

Note. Data collected on patients 65 and older. A, Admission; D, Discharge; EX, expired; H, Home; NH, Nursing Home; OH, Other Hospitals.

Attention

Attention was assessed daily at each assessment time. It was measured by using Month of the Year Backwards (MOTYB) testing. O'Regan et al. (2014) evaluated and compared different simple cognitive screening methods for their usefulness and accuracy. They found that MOTYB has high sensitivity (93.8%) and specificity (84.7%) to identify confusion among older adults (O'Regan et al., 2014). For this test, the investigator asked the patient to name the months of the year forward from January to December. Then, the patient was asked to name the months of the year in reverse. The patient passed the test if she or he correctly recited the months from December back to as far as July. After administering the MOTYB, the PI proceeded to the CAM-ICU on all patients.

Delirium Screening

The CAM-ICU was used to screen delirium. The CAM-ICU has been validated in the ED and inpatient units. It is a shorter version of the CAM. The CAM-ICU takes 2-3 minutes to perform, has a high sensitivity (93-100 %) and specificity (98-100 %) and high inter-rater reliability ($K = .77- .95$) (Han et al., 2009). The CAM-ICU evaluates patients for (a) acute onset of confusion, (b) inattention, (c) altered level of consciousness, and (d) disorganized thinking (Han et al., 2009). If the patient receives a positive score for confusion and inattention, plus a positive score for altered level of consciousness or disorganized thinking, the patient has delirium (Boehm, Pun, & Stollings, 2016). If scores for (a) and (b) are negative, the patient is not delirious (Appendix I).

The third step in CAM-ICU assessment is to evaluate the level of consciousness using the Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale (RASS) (See Appendix J). Since the RASS assesses patients for both agitation and sedation level, it can be used in all patients regardless of whether they are receiving sedation or not (Boehm et al., 2016). The 10-item RASS scores the patient from +4 (combative) to -5 (unarousable). In this scale, zero is the normal baseline (alert and calm). A RASS score other than zero is considered an altered level of consciousness (Boehm et al., 2016) (Appendix J)

The PI, an RN, has the background knowledge in using cognitive and delirium assessment tools. In summer 2018, she received online training and in-servicing from a critical care educator (Co, 2018) who is an expert on CAM-ICU training.

Documentation of Delirium

As part of baseline assessment, medical records were reviewed for documentation of delirium or its signs/symptoms, altered mental status, medications, and past medical history. Documentation regarding medications and diagnosis of dementia helped in choosing appropriate patients. The past medical history was used for the Charlson comorbidity index evaluation to predict mortality risk. Documentation on delirium or altered level of consciousness by the emergency department RN or MD was evaluated separately as a variable in delirium recognition at the time of admission.

Functional Level

Patient functional levels were measured using the Katz Activities of Daily Living (Katz ADL). Katz ADL scores patient functional level for performing personal care, bathing, dressing, toileting, transferring, continence, and feeding, with two level scales of 0 and 1, where 0 indicates dependence and 1 independence in performing ADLs. See the copy of this tool in Appendix G.

Comorbidity Index

The Charlson comorbidity index at the time of admission (Appendix H) was calculated. This index served as a predictor for 10-year mortality for patients with chronic medical conditions. Each condition is assigned a score between 1-6 depending on the risk of death related to the condition (Rattanasompattikul et al., 2012). Charlson comorbidity index was calculated for each patient in this study as a covariable that might affect LOS and discharge destination.

Other Measures

The hospital LOS (days of hospitalization) and discharge destination (home vs nursing home, transfer to ICU, or death) were collected from the medical records. A decline in physical function was evaluated by comparing the patient's functional level at the time of admission to functional status at the time of discharge. The data on secondary outcomes (the use of sitters, and restraints during this hospitalization and falls prior hospitalization or during hospitalization) were collected using a simple yes/no for each variable. These data were collected from medical records or during PI observations. Patient's reported medical diagnosis also was collected from medical record.

Data Collection

Data was collected from September to November 2018. During week days, the PI collected data from 1500 – 2100, and at various times on the weekends depending on the hospital census. The investigator anticipated registering approximately 300 patients (minimum of 5 patients each day); however, of 430 patients who were screened, only 204 consented to participate.

Patients admitted from ED in the prior 12 hours and ED patients were screened every day of the week for eligibility to participate in the study. Following enrollment, patients were assessed on the non-ICU units for up to three days.

Data Analysis

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 25.0)TM software was used to analyze the data. Two-tail testing was used with $p \leq .05$ considered significant. Incident delirium was a created binary variable (never delirious during the first three days vs delirious during the first three days). The initial power calculation for sample size

suggested that minimum total sample of 202 would be enough for a *t*-test or one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with a moderate effect size of 0.4 and statistical power of 0.88 and probability of 0.05.

Continuous variables were analyzed with means and standard deviations (SD), and dichotomous/categorical variables were analyzed with frequencies and percentages. Chi-Square, *phi* coefficient (ϕ), and ANOVA were used in analyzing the associations between incident delirium with pre-hospitalization patient characteristics (gender, age, living status, history of falls prior to admission, altered level of consciousness in the ED, Charlson comorbidity index, functional level before hospitalization) during hospitalization characteristics (use of sitters, restraints, falls, medical diagnosis, observed /reported by nurse), and post-hospitalization characteristics per medical record review (length of stay, disposition after discharge).

To determine whether baseline or pre-hospital characteristics predicted delirium incidence, variables with significant bivariate associations with delirium incidence were used as predictors in a binary logistic regression. To determine whether delirium incidence predicted hospital LOS and post-hospital disposition (home, nursing home, ICU, and transfer to another hospital), a general linear model was run with incident delirium as the fixed predictor factor and post-hospitalization variables with significant bivariate associations with delirium as dependent variables.

RESULTS

The purpose of this study was to report the incidence of delirium and its association with LOS, discharge destination, and discharge functional level among hospitalized older patients admitted to non-ICU units through the ED. The associations between incident delirium and the use of sitters, restraints, falls, and nurse observed and reported cases of delirium were analyzed as well.

A total of 430 patients were screened and 121 patients were eliminated after chart review. Out of 309 eligible patients, 62 refused to participate, and 43 patients were not available or were sleeping when approached for consent. Thus, 204 patients consented to participate. The flowchart of patient accrual is illustrated in Figure 2.

Baseline characteristics of patients are reported in Table 3. Out of 204 patients, 84 (41.2%) were male, and 120 (58.8%) were female. The age distribution ranged from 65 to 101 years with an average age of 80.9. Upon baseline evaluation, only three patients were living at a nursing home with the majority of patients (201 or 98.5 %) coming from a home, assisted living, or residential care facilities (labeled as *home* for further analysis). The total hospital LOS was between 1 to 18 days, with an average of 4.21 days. Most patients (78.4%) were discharged home from the hospital; upon discharge, 36 patients (17.6%) were transferred to skilled nursing facilities due to the need for extended care, 5 (2.5%) were transferred to a higher level of care within the hospital, and 3 (1.3%) were transferred to another acute hospital.

Out of 204 patients, 149 did not have a positive delirium screening during the three days of assessment (this group was labeled delirium negative), and 55 (27%) patients (who labeled delirium positive) were assessed positively for delirium by CAM-

ICU at least one of three days of assessment. Table 3 shows the differences in demographic and clinical factors of patients with and without incident delirium.

Figure 2. Flowchart of patient accrual

Emergency nurses reported altered level of consciousness on 25 patients in their ED-nursing assessment. Out of 25 patients who had altered level of consciousness at home, 22 (88 %) were later found to be delirium positive during their first three days of hospitalization (Table 3).

The association between delirium incidence and age, gender, living status, LOS, discharge destination, restraint usage during hospitalization, sitters usage during hospitalization, functional level, falls and Charlson comorbidity index were examined. As illustrated in Table 3, there are significant relationships between delirium incidence and age, where the average age for delirium negative patients was 80.3 years ($SD = 8.3$) and for the delirium positive patients was 82.6 ($SD = 6.7$; $p = .039$). The discharge disposition among patients with positive delirium to a nursing home, ICU, or transfer to another hospital had significant associations with delirium incidence ($p = .003$); delirium positive patients were more likely to be discharged to non-home settings than those without incident delirium. Altered level of consciousness at home ($p < .0001$), the use of a sitter during hospitalization ($p = .018$), use of restraints during hospital stay ($p < .0001$), the length of hospital stay ($p = .003$), and functional level at the time of admission ($p = .002$) all had statistically significant relationships to delirium during the first three days of hospitalization.

Findings indicate that patients with incident delirium were more likely to need a sitter or restraints, and have a lower functional level on admission (see Table 3). Charlson comorbidity index did not show a significant association with delirium ($p = .341$). Out of 48 patients who screened delirium positive on the first day of admission only 7 (14.5 %) had a medical diagnosis of altered level of consciousness, delirium, or encephalopathy. Twenty four patients (11.8 %) had an incident of fall at home (before admission), and 9 (16.4 %) of them were screened positive for delirium in ED. However, during hospitalization, only 1 (.5%) patient had an incident of falling (Table 3).

Table 3

Demographic Data, Baseline Characteristics, and Clinical Findings for Hospitalized Patients with and without Incident Delirium

Characteristic	Total Sample (n = 204)	Delirium Negative (n = 149)	Delirium Positive (n = 55)	p-value
Before hospitalization (baseline)				
Gender, n (%)				
Male	84 (41.2)	60 (71.4)	24 (28.6)	.664
Female	120 (58.8)	89 (74.2)	31 (25.8)	
Age, M (SD)	80.9 (7.9)	80.3 (8.3)	82.6 (6.7)	.039 *
65-101				
Living status upon admission, n (%)				
Home	201 (98.5)	146 (72.6)	55 (27.4)	.289
Nursing home	3 (1.5)	3 (100)	0	
Reported altered level of conscious in ED, n (%)				
No	179 (87.7)	146 (81.6)	33 (18.4)	.000* (ϕ)
Yes	25 (12.3)	3 (12)	22 (88)	
Pre-admission fall, n (%)				
No	180 (88.2)	134 (74.4)	46 (83.6)	.215
Yes	24 (11.8)	15 (62.5)	9 (16.4)	
Charlson Comorbidity Index, M (SD)	7.19 (2.07)	7.11 (2.15)	7.42 (2.15)	.341
4-13				
Function Level in admission (Katz ADL), M (SD)	5.50 (1.25)	5.66 (1.03)	5.06 (1.65)	.002*
During hospitalization				
Sitter, n (%)				
No	201 (99.0)	149 (74.1)	52 (25.9)	.018*
Yes	2 (1.0)	(0)	2 (100)	
Restraint, n (%)				
No	188 (92.2)	148 (78.7)	40 (72.3)	.000*
Yes	15 (7.4)	1 (1.6)	14 (25.5)	
Fall, n (%)				
No	201(98.5)	148(73)	53 (45.5)	.194 (ϕ)
Yes	2 (1)	1 (.5)	1 (.5)	
Observation report by nurse, n (%)				
No	191 (93.6)	147 (77.0)	44 (23.0)	.000*
Yes	12 (5.9)	2 (16.7)	10 (83.3)	
Post-hospitalization				
Length of hospital stay (days), M (SD)	4.21 (2.63)	3.79 (3.68)	5.39 (3.68)	.003 *
1-18				
Disposition at hospital discharge, n (%)				
Home	160 (78.4)			.003 *
Nursing home	36 (17.6)			
ICU	5 (2.5)			
Hospital (transfer)	3 (1.5)			

Note. *Indicates significant level.

Nurse observations and recognition of delirium are important elements in delirium management and program development. Nurses in non-ICU units documented the change of mental status or confusion in 12 (5.9%) patients out of 55 delirium positive patients. Of these, 10 (83.3%) patients were found to be CAM positive by the PI, $\Phi (\phi) = .318, p < .0001$. This finding shows that some nurses are using professional assessment skills to identify behavioral changes in these patients despite not being trained in delirium assessment. However, lack of written observations were found for 45/55 (81.8 %) of patients with incident delirium during their stay. This relationship is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Documented nurse observation of positive delirium for three days of observation

In Table 4, percentages of patients with poor level of attention (failure on MOTYB) and incident delirium is shown for each of the three days of patient assessments. On the first day, out of 203 patients, 60 (29.6 %) patients had inattention

and 48 (23.5%) were delirium positive. For the second day, 43 (22.9%) patients showed inattention with 37 (19.7%) having delirium, and on the third day, 32 (23%) had inattention with 27 (19.6 %) delirium.

Table 4

Cognitive Tests Over Three Days

Test	Day1	Day 2	Day 3
Failed Month of the Year Backwards, <i>n</i> (%)	60 (29.6) ^a	43 (22.9)	32 (23.0)
Delirium Positive, <i>n</i> (%)	48 (23.5)	37 (19.7)	27 (19.6) ^b

Note. ^a*n* = 203. ^b*n* = 138

Patient functional level was assessed at baseline and on each assessment day using the Katz ADL tool. As seen in Table 5, the proportion of patients with high functional levels (scores of 5 or 6) decreased over the three days of assessment. Out of 203 patients observed, 183 (78.8 %) had functional levels of 5 or 6 at baseline. On day one, only 100 patients (63.8 %) had functional levels of 5-6, and by day three of observation, out of 145 patients were observed, only 69 (47.8 %) had functional levels of 5-6 (see Table 5 for functional status from baseline through day 3).

The comparison between the functional level in each of the three screening days with functional level day zero showed significant differences. Consistent with this, mean functional levels also decreased as seen in Figure 4. There was a significant difference between the functional level of all patients, with delirium and without delirium, during each day of observation (see Table 6). For all patients (with/without incident delirium), baseline functional level was higher than the functional level on any of the other days of assessment (as shown by oneway ANOVAs, *p*'s < .0001).

Table 5

Functional Status from Baseline Through Day 3

Function	Baseline	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
Number of cases	203	204	193	145
<i>n</i> (%) with score of 5 or 6*	183 (78.8)	100 (63.8)	96 (49.7)	69 (47.8)

Note. *6 is highest level of independency.

Figure 4. Mean functional levels for all patients from baseline to day three of observation.

The average LOS for patient hospitalizations was 4.21 days ($SD = 2.63$) days, where delirium patients had an average LOS of 5.39 ($SD = 3.68$) and non-delirious patients 3.79 ($SD = 3.68$), $p = .003$ (see Table 3). Table 6 indicates the association of functional level and length of stay in delirious and nondelirious patients; patients exhibiting delirium had lower average functional scores on each day assessed than did patients with no delirium. Patients with delirium also had longer lengths of hospital stay than did those without, $F(1) = 64.403$, $p = .003$. Lower functional scores on each day were associated with longer lengths of stay among delirious patients, $F(1) = 62.888$, $p \leq .0001$.

To evaluate patient discharge destination in relation to delirium incidence, Chi-squared was performed. The significant association between discharge destination and having delirium is illustrated in Table 7. Out of 55 patients who had delirium, 35 (63.6%) were discharged home, 14 (25.5 %) were transferred to nursing homes, 4 (7.3 %) were transferred to a higher level of care (ICU), and 2 (3.6%) were transferred to another hospital, $\chi^2(3) = 14.856, p = .002$. Table 7 shows that the proportions of patients with incident delirium who were discharged to a nursing home, intensive care unit, or were transferred to another hospital were greater than patients without delirium.

Table 6

Associations Between Delirium and Functional Status Across Three Days and Length of Stay

	Delirium Positive			Delirium Negative			<i>p</i> -value ^a
	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	95 % <i>CI</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	95 % <i>CI</i>	
Functional status (day 3)	44	2.23 (1.90)	[1.63, 2.81]	101	4.21 (1.36)	[3.94, 4.48]	.000
Functional status (day 2)	51	2.22 (1.82)	[1.71, 2.73]	142	4.35 (1.24)	[4.14, 4.55]	.000
Functional status (day 1)	55	2.29 (1.87)	[1.78, 2.80]	149	4.38 (1.26)	[4.18, 4.59]	.000
Baseline functional status (FD0)	54	5.06 (1.653) (<i>n</i> = 54)	[5.49, 5.82]	149	5.66 (1.025)	[4.60, 5.51]	.002
Length of stay	54	5.39 (3.68)	[4.39, 6.39]	149	3.79 (1.98)	[3.47, 4.10]	.003

Note. ^aTested using one-way ANOVA; all analyses showed significant differences across group variances, so Welch's F tests were used.

Table 7

Association Between Delirium and Disposition Status for Patients Who Entered the Hospital from Home (n = 201)

Delirium Status	Disposition				Total
	Home	Nursing Home	ICU	Hospital (transfer)	
Positive	35 (63.6%)	14 (25.5)	4 (7.3)	2 (3.6)	55
Negative	124 (84.9%)	20 (13.7)	1 (0.7)	1 (0.7)	146
Total	159 (79.1)	34 (16.9)	5 (2.5)	3 (1.5)	201

Note. $X^2(3) = 14.86, p = .002$.

To determine whether baseline or pre-hospital characteristics predicted delirium incidence, variables with significant bivariate associations with delirium incidence were used as predictors in a binary logistic regression (see Table 8). Ages, altered level of consciousness as reported by family in the ED, and baseline Katz ADL score (higher functional level with higher scores) were these predictors. The model predicted poorly as shown by the significant Hosmer and Lemeshow test. However, there were independent contributions to the prediction of delirium incidence by reported altered level of consciousness by family in the ED and baseline functional level (Katz ADL score). Family reports of altered level of consciousness in the ED made it less likely that patients would have incident delirium after taking age and baseline function into account. Having a lower baseline functional level predicted delirium incidence, taking into account age and family-reported altered level of consciousness (Table 8).

Table 8

Summary Table of Logistic Regression Analysis for Pre-Hospital Patient Characteristics Predicting Incident Delirium (n = 55)

	Unstandardized coefficient		df	Significance	OR	95% CI	
	B	SE				Lower	Upper
Age	.014	.024	1	.541	1.015	.969	1.063
Altered level of consciousness	-3.335	.654	1	.000	.036	.010	.128
Baseline function	-.287	.138	1	.037	.750	.573	.982

Note. OR = odds ratio. Hosmer and Lemeshow test, $X^2(8) = 16.770$, $p = .033$. Nagelkerke $R^2 = .324$.

To determine whether delirium incidence predicted hospital LOS and post-hospital disposition (0 = home; 1 = not home), a general linear model was run with incident delirium as the fixed predictor factor and LOS and disposition as dependent variables. In the corrected model, incident delirium predicted LOS, $F(1) = 8.936$, $p = .003$, adjusted $R^2 = .068$, and disposition, $F(1) = 15.834$, $p < .0001$, adjusted $R^2 = .038$.

DISCUSSION

This study showed that 27 % of patients 65 years or older entering non-critical hospitals floors from the ED had an incident of delirium at least once during three days of assessment, confirming findings from previous studies (Johansson, Bergh, Ericsson, & Sarenmalm, 2018; Kukreja, Gunther, & Popp, 2015). These patients had delirium unrecognized by staff in most cases. The findings also showed that there were significant relationships between delirium and longer hospital LOS, discharge disposition to a place besides home, and lower functional levels at baseline and throughout the three assessment days. The use of restraints and sitters also were higher among delirium patients, indicating increased resource use.

Factors Associated with Delirium

Although not statistically significant, LOS was about 1.6 days longer for delirium patients making this an important resource issue when care compensation is often bundled by insurers. Others have found that unrecognized delirium does not statistically increase LOS; however, it may negatively affect readmission rates and patient outcomes after discharge (Han et al., 2011; Han et al., 2017; McCusker, Cole, Dendukuri, & Belzile, 2003).

The reported data on the average cost of care for not-for-profit hospitals in California in 2003 was about \$ 3500 for a night, and considering the current inflation rate, the cost of a one-night hospital stay would be about \$4000. Last year, 7000 patients were admitted from the ED to non-ICU units in the study site. A simple cost calculation of approximately two extra days (1.6 days) in the hospital for these patients would be about \$12,000,000 ($7000 \times 1.6 \times .27 \times \$4000 = \$12,096,000$) a year. This calculation does

not include the cost of readmissions or consider delirium in patients with dementia. Still, it shows that the hospital might have potential significant cost savings by managing delirium.

In doing the assessments across three days of hospitalization for patients in this study, the PI noted that many patients were not expected to care for themselves and were not mobilized during these days of their hospital stay. This observation may explain the rationale for the lower functional level seen after baseline during those three days for all patients. This is particularly important since multivariate analysis showed that lower baseline function predicted incident delirium. The limited self-care performed by patients could also be the reason for these patients not having reported falls during hospitalization. Limiting patients' ambulation to prevent falls has recently been discussed as a risk factor for deconditioning and lower function (Cho et al., 2018). Since limiting patients from performing self-care, especially ambulation, is a known risk factor for delirium (Inouye et al., 1999), it is essential to address hospitalized patients' limited functions with interventions that address this issue.

The Charlson comorbidity index has been used in previous delirium recognition studies with no significant associations found between the index and delirium (Han et al., 2009; Hsieh et al., 2017). Similarly, in this study, the Charlson comorbidity index showed a nonsignificant relationship to delirium as well. For future studies, use of LACE scores which incorporate patient LOS, acuity at the time of admission, comorbidity, and the

number of emergency department visits may be considered instead of Charlson comorbidity index.

The association between scores on the MOTYB and CAM-ICU in this study showed that not all patients who had inattention (failed MOTYB) had positive CAM-ICU. This finding might indicate that MOTYB tool might not be the best choice for assessing inattention. This author suggests that the cognitive deficit found with MOTYB inattention tool may be associated with cognitive changes related to aging. This point is important to consider for choosing screening tool, since some delirium screening tools, such as b-CAM use the imbedded MOTYB as the element of inattention.

Delirium Recognition

The findings of this study showed that only 7 (14.5 %) patients who were admitted from ED to non- ICU units had a medical diagnosis as altered level of consciousness, delirium, or encephalopathy. Thus, 85.5 % of patients who were found to have incident delirium during early hospitalization were not reported as delirious by ED or admitting physicians. In previous studies, researchers reported 7-10 % of delirium incidents happened in the ED, and of those up to 87 % cases were not identified by ED or admitting physicians (Grossmann et al., 2014; Hasemann et al., 2017). Educating care providers to use standard screening tools can increase knowledge and awareness about delirium and help to identify more incident delirium and guide the initiation of appropriate interventions (Yanamadala et al., 2013).

Early delirium recognition is essential in improving patient outcomes (Han et al., 2009; Hsieh et al., 2015). Han et al. identified the lack of using screening tools as the primary cause of under-recognized delirium in the ED (2009). They emphasized that staff

can improve delirium recognition rate by evaluating delirium risk factors such as dementia, present of infection, a decrease in ADL levels, and hearing impairment. Studies confirm that educating nurses about delirium and the use of screening tools can increase delirium recognition rates (Filinson et al., 2016; El Hussein et al., 2015). In this study, ED nurses reported patient confusion in the ED or at home before coming to ED in about 12.3 % (25) of cases versus 23.5 % (48 patients) who were CAM positive in the first 12 hours of admission. This finding shows the need for nursing education in the ED to improve delirium recognition.

Nurses on the non-ICU floors documented cognition changes in the medical records for only 12 (21.8%) of the 55 patients with incident delirium. While a minority of nurses were able to identify and report mental status changes, further education is needed to increase the reporting rate and nurses' confidence in their assessment and delirium management.

Introducing a standard delirium screening tool can decrease the rate of unrecognized delirium. Studies have confirmed that using such tools can increase nursing knowledge and help with the recognition of delirium (Steege et al., 2014; Yanamadala et al., 2013). For a change to become a permanent practice habit, educators should explain the reasons for the expected behavioral change and its benefits for patients; also, the leadership needs to be open to receive feedback from nurses and modify the practice changes based on the observations (Steege et al., 2014). A plan to develop a delirium prevention and management program should be comprehensive and should have continuity (McCrow et al., 2013). Therefore, a multidisciplinary approach where

leadership, physicians, and nurses are involved in delirium management would be beneficial for the success of the delirium prevention and management programs.

Limitations

There are limitations to this study related to its design that could influence the observed incident delirium. Most patients were recruited from non-ICU units during the first 12 hours from the patient's admission and not in the ED. Therefore, the findings of this study primarily reflect incident delirium in entering inpatient units from the ED rather than incident delirium assessed in the ED.

Limiting data collection to the first three days of hospitalization enabled this study to have a snapshot of incident delirium during this period. However, some cases of delirium may have happened after the three days of assessment. Those cases were not included in this study.

Another limitation of this study was excluding patients with dementia. Excluding dementia patients from the study was purposeful, since determining delirium in dementia patients is challenging and a cognitive assessment of patients with dementia might require specialized training (El Hussein et al., 2015). However, the exclusion of dementia patients probably led to underreporting of incident delirium on non-critical care units.

Evaluating delirium in stroke patients was another limitation of this study. Although stroke was not one of the exclusion criteria, the PI excluded cerebrovascular accident (CVA) patients with expressive aphasia and patients who had temporary cognitive impairment secondary to stroke. Delirium among stroke patients would be a subject for another study.

Conclusions

This study confirmed a clinically significant number of older patients exhibiting incident delirium during early non-ICU hospitalization. These patients were exposed to

higher use of sitters and restraints at the hospital and experienced increased lengths of stay and were discharged to higher levels of care than were patients without incident delirium. They also suffered decreased functional levels throughout their early hospitalizations.

For approximately two decades researchers have been discussing the high incidence of delirium among older patients in non-ICU units. This study supported the low rates of delirium recognition by untrained staff and medical personnel, and the high financial and personal costs related to delirium and its outcomes. Findings support the need for using one of the many effective delirium recognition and management programs in the study setting.

REFERENCES

- Angel, C., Brooks, K., & Fourie, J. (2016). Standardizing management of adults with delirium hospitalized on medical-surgical units. *the Permanente Journal*, 20(4), 27-32. doi:10.7812/tpp/16-002
- Baczynska, A. M., Lim, S. E., Sayer, A. A., & Roberts, H. C. (2016). The use of volunteers to help older medical patients mobilize in hospital: A systematic review. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 25(21-22), 3102-3112. doi:10.1111/jocn.13317
- Bakker, F. C., Persoon, A., Bredie, S. J. H., van Haren-Willems, J., Leferink, V. J., Noyez, L., . . . Olde Rikkert, M. G. M. (2014). The CareWell in hospital program to improve the quality of care for frail elderly inpatients: Results of a before-after study with focus on surgical patients. *American Journal of Surgery*, 208(5), 735-746. doi:10.1016/j.amjsurg.2014.04.009
- Barman, A., Pradhan, D., Bhattacharyya, P., Dey, S., Bhattacharjee, A., Tesia, S. S., & Mitra, J. K. (2018). Diagnostic accuracy of delirium assessment methods in critical care patients. *Journal of Critical Care*, 44, 82-86. doi:10.1016/j.jcrc.2017.10.013
- Barron, E. A., & Holmes, J. (2013). Delirium within the emergency care setting, occurrence and detection: A systematic review. *British Medical Journal* 30, 263. doi:10.1136/emered-2011-200586
- Boehm, L., Pun, B., & Stollings, J. (2016, August 31, 2016). Confusion assessment method for the ICU (CAM-ICU), The complete training manual. Retrieved from <http://www.icudelirium.org/resources.html>

- Boockvar, K. S., Teresi, J. A., & Inouye, S. K. (2016). Preliminary data: An adapted hospital elder life program to prevent delirium and reduce complications of acute illness in long-term care delivered by certified nursing assistants. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society, 64*(5), 1108. doi:10.1111/jgs.14091
- Bradley, E. H., Schlesinger, M., Webster, T. R., Baker, D., & Inouye, S. K. (2004). Translating research into clinical practice: Making change happen. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society, 52*(11), 1875-1882. doi:10.1111/j.1532-5415.2004.52510.x
- Bradley, E. H., Webster, T. R., Baker, D., Schlesinger, M., & Inouye, S. K. (2005). After adoption: Sustaining the innovation, a case study of disseminating the Hospital Elder Life Program. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society, 53*(9), 1455-1461. doi:10.1111/j.1532-5415.2005.53451.x
- Cho, H. J., Dunn, A. S., Sakai, Y., Israilov, S., Raja, A., Race, J., & Leipzig, R. M. (2018). Choosing wisely to mobilize patients in reducing falls and injury. *The Joint Commission Journal on Quality and Patient Safety, 44*(8), 500-501. doi:10.1016/j.jcjq.2018.03.003
- Chong, M. S., Chan, M. P. C., Kang, J., Han, H. C., Ding, Y. Y., & Tan, T. L. (2011). A new model of delirium care in the acute geriatric setting: Geriatric monitoring unit. *BioMedical Center Medicine, 11*, 41-41. doi:10.1186/1471-2318-11-41
- Co, Z. (2018) Enhancing screening and management of delirium in critical care. Retrieved from:
http://nursing.fullerton.edu/programs/pdf/dnp/finalprojects/2018/Co_23%202018-05-17%20Co%20DNP%20FINAL_5_21.pdf

- De, J., & Wand, A. P. F. (2015). Delirium Screening: A Systematic Review of Delirium Screening Tools in Hospitalized Patients. *The Gerontologist, 55*(6), 1079-1099. doi:10.1093/geront/gnv100
- De Marchis, G. M., Foderaro, G., Jemora, J., Zanchi, F., Altobianchi, A., Biglia, E., . . . Mombelli, G. (2010). Mild cognitive impairment in medical inpatients: The mini-mental state examination is a promising screening tool. *Dementia and Geriatric Cognitive Disorders, 29*(3), 259-264. doi:10.1159/000288772
- Dyer, A. H., Briggs, R., Nabeel, S., O'Neill, D., & Kennelly, S. P. (2017). The abbreviated mental test 4 for cognitive screening of older adults presenting to the Emergency Department. *European Journal Emergency Medicine, 24*(6), 417-422. doi:10.1097/mej.0000000000000394
- El Hussein, M., Hirst, S., & Salyers, V. (2015). Factors that contribute to underrecognition of delirium by registered nurses in acute care settings: a scoping review of the literature to explain this phenomenon. *Journal of Clinical Nursing, 24*(7-8), 906-915. doi:10.1111/jocn.12693
- Emond, M., Grenier, D., Morin, J., Eagles, D., Boucher, V., Le Sage, N., . . . Lee, J. S. (2017). Emergency department stay associated delirium in older patients. *Canadian Geriatrics Journal, 20*(1), 10-14. doi:10.5770/cgj.20.246
- Filinson, R., Clark, P., Burbank, P., & Stoukides, J. (2016). Adoption of delirium assessment in the acute care setting: A tale of two hospitals. *Best Practices in Mental Health, 12*(2), 81-95.

- Fortini, A., Morettini, A., Tavernese, G., Facchini, S., Tofani, L., & Pazzi, M. (2014). Delirium in elderly patients hospitalized in internal medicine wards. *Intern Emergency Medicine*, 9(4), 435-441. doi:10.1007/s11739-013-0968-0
- Freter, S., Koller, K., Dunbar, M., Macknight, C., & Rockwood, K. (2017). Translating delirium prevention strategies for elderly adults with hip fracture into routine clinical care: A pragmatic clinical trial. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 65(3), 567-573. doi:10.1111/jgs.14568
- Gelinas, C., Berbbe, M., Chavrier, a., Pun, B., Ely, W., Skrobik, Y., & Barr, J. (2018). Delirium assessment tools for use in critically ill adults: a psychometric analysis and systemic review. *Critical Care Nurse*, 38(1), 38-50.
- Godfrey, M., Smith, J., Green, J., Cheater, F., Inouye, S. K., & Young, J. B. (2013). Developing and implementing an integrated delirium prevention system of care: A theory driven, participatory research study. *BioMedical Center Health Services Research*. doi:10.1186/1472-6963-13-341
- Grossmann, F. F., Hasemann, W., Graber, A., Bingisser, R., Kressig, R. W., & Nickel, C. H. (2014). Screening, detection and management of delirium in the emergency department - a pilot study on the feasibility of a new algorithm for use in older emergency department patients: The modified Confusion Assessment Method for the Emergency Department (mCAM-ED). *Scandinavian Journal of Trauma, Resuscitation and Emergency Medicine* 22, 19. doi:10.1186/1757-7241-22-19

- Grossmann, F. F., Hasemann, W., Kressig, R. W., Bingisser, R., & Nickel, C. H. (2017). Performance of the modified Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale in identifying delirium in older ED patients. *The American Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 35(9), 1324-1326. doi:10.1016/j.ajem.2017.05.025
- Han, J. H., Eden, S., Shintani, A., Morandi, A., Schnelle, J., Dittus, R. S., . . . Ely, E. W. (2011). Delirium in older emergency department patients is an independent predictor of hospital length of stay. *Academic Emergency Medicine*, 18(5), 451-457. doi:10.1111/j.1553-2712.2011.01065.x
- Han, J. H., Schnelle, J. F., & Ely, E. W. (2014). The relationship between a chief complaint of "altered mental status" and delirium in older emergency department patients. *Academic Emergency Medicine*, 21(8), 937-940. doi:10.1111/acem.12436
- Han, J. H., Shintani, A., Eden, S., Morandi, A., Solberg, L. M., Schnelle, J., . . . Ely, E. W. (2010). Delirium in the emergency department: An independent predictor of death within 6 months. *Annals of Emergency Medicine*, 56(3), 244-252.e241. doi:10.1016/j.annemergmed.2010.03.003
- Han, J. H., Vasilevskis, E. E., Chandrasekhar, R., Liu, X., Schnelle, J. F., Dittus, R. S., & Ely, E. W. (2017). Delirium in the emergency department and its extension into hospitalization (DELINEATE) study: Effect on 6-month function and cognition. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 65(6), 1333-1338. doi:10.1111/jgs.14824

- Han, J. H., Wilson, A., Vasilevskis, E. E., Shintani, A., Schnelle, J. F., Dittus, R. S., . . . Ely, E. W. (2013). Diagnosing delirium in older emergency department patients: Validity and reliability of the delirium triage screen and the brief confusion assessment method. *Annals of Emergency Medicine*, *62*(5), 457-465. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annemergmed.2013.05.003>
- Han, J. H., Zimmerman, E. E., Cutler, N., Schnelle, J., Morandi, A., Dittus, R. S., . . . Wesley Ely, E. (2009). Delirium in older emergency department patients: Recognition, risk factors, and psychomotor subtypes. *Academic Emergency Medicine*, *16*(3), 193-200. doi:[10.1111/j.1553-2712.2008.00339.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1553-2712.2008.00339.x)
- Harrison, J. R. (2017). Improving inpatient care for older adults: Implementing dementia commissioning for quality and innovation (CQUIN). *British Medical Journal Quality Improvement Reports*, *6*(1). doi:[10.1136/bmjquality.u212202.w4875](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjquality.u212202.w4875)
- Hasemann, W., Grossmann, F. F., Stadler, R., Bingisser, R., Breil, D., Hafner, M., . . . Nickel, C. H. (2017). Screening and detection of delirium in older ED patients: performance of the modified Confusion Assessment Method for the Emergency Department (mCAM-ED). A two-step tool. *Internal Emergency Medicine*. doi:[10.1007/s11739-017-1781-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11739-017-1781-y)
- Heim, N., van Fenema, E. M., Weverling-Rijnsburger, A. W. E., Tuijl, J. P., Jue, P., Oleksik, A. M., . . . Westendorp, R. G. J. (2015). Optimal screening for increased risk for adverse outcomes in hospitalised older adults. *Age and Ageing*, *44*(2), 239-244. doi:[10.1093/ageing/afu187](https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afu187)

- Hipp, D., & Ely, E. (2012). Pharmacological and nonpharmacological management of delirium in critically ill patients. *The Journal of the American Society for Experimental NeuroTherapeutics*, *9*(1), 158-175. doi:10.1007/s13311-011-0102-9
- Hshieh, T. T., Inouye, S. K., & Oh, E. S. (2018). Delirium in the elderly. *Psychiatric Clinics of North America*, *41*(1), 1-17. doi:10.1016/j.psc.2017.10.001
- Hsieh, S. J., Madahar, P., Hope, A. A., Zapata, J., & Gong, M. N. (2015). Clinical deterioration in older adults with delirium during early hospitalisation: A prospective cohort study. *British Medical Journal Open*, *5*(9). doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2014-007496
- Inouye, S. K., Bogardus, S., Baker, D., Leo-Summers, L., & Cooney, L. (2000). The Hospital Elder Life Program: A model of care to prevent cognitive and functional decline in older hospitalized patients. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, *48*(12), 1697-1706.
- Inouye, S. K., Bogardus, S. T., Baker, D. I., Leo-Summers, L., & Cooney, L. M. (2000). Models of geriatrics practice; The Hospital Elder Life Program: A model of care to prevent cognitive and functional decline in older hospitalized patients. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, *48*(12), 1697-1706. doi:10.1111/j.1532-5415.2000.tb03885.x
- Inouye, S. K., Bogardus, S. T., Charpentier, P. A., Leo-Summers, L., Acampora, D., Holford, T. R., & Cooney, L. M. (1999). A multicomponent intervention to prevent delirium in hospitalized older patients. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, *340*. doi:10.1056/nejm199903043400901

- Inouye, S. K., Robinson, T., Blaum, C., Busby-Whitehead, J., Boustani, M., Chalian, A., . . . MJ., S. I. (2015). American Geriatrics Society abstracted clinical practice guideline for postoperative delirium in older adults. *Journal of American Geriatrics Society*, 63(1), 142-150. doi:10.1111/jgs.13281
- Inouye, S. K., Westendorp, R. G., Saczynski, J. S., Kimchi, E. Y., & Cleinman, A. A. (2014). Delirium in elderly people--authors'reply. *Lancet*, 383(9934), 2045. doi:10.1016/s0140-6736(14)60994-6
- Inouye, S. K., Zhang, Y., Jones, R. N., Shi, P., Cupples, L. A., Calderon, H. N., & Marcantonio, E. R. (2008). Risk factors for hospitalization among community-dwelling primary care older patients: development and validation of a predictive model. *Medical Care*, 46. doi:10.1097/MLR.0b013e3181649426
- Jaccard, J., Helbig, D. W., Wan, C. K., Gutman, M. A., & Kritz-Silverstein, D. C. (1996). The prediction of accurate contraceptive use from attitudes and knowledge. *Health Education Quarterly*, 23(1), 17-33.
- Johansson, Y. A., Bergh, I., Ericsson, I., & Sarenmalm, E. K. (2018). Delirium in older hospitalized patients-signs and actions: a retrospective patient record review. *BMC Geriatr*, 18(1), 43. doi:10.1186/s12877-018-0731-5
- Karki, S., Bhatta, D. N., & Aryal, U. R. (2015). Older people's perspectives on an elderly-friendly hospital environment: an exploratory study. *Risk Manag Healthc Policy*, 8, 81-89. doi:10.2147/rmhp.s83008

- Kuczmarska, A., Ngo, L. H., Guess, J., O'Connor, M. A., Branford-White, L., Palihnich, K., . . . Marcantonio, E. R. (2016). Detection of delirium in hospitalized older general medicine patients: A comparison of the 3D-CAM and CAM-ICU. *Journal of General Internal Medicine, 31*(3), 297-303. doi:10.1007/s11606-015-3514-0
- Kukreja, D., Gunther, U., & Popp, J. (2015). Delirium in the elderly: Current problems with increasing geriatric age. *Indian J Med Res, 142*(6), 655-662. doi:10.4103/0971-5916.174546
- LaMantia, M. A., Messina, F. C., Hobgood, C. D., & Miller, D. K. (2014). Screening for delirium in the emergency department: a systematic review. *Annals of Emergency Medicine, 63*(5), 551-560. e552.
- Leslie, D., & Inouye, S. (2011). The importance of delirium: Economic and societal costs. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society, 59 Suppl 2*, S241-243. doi:10.1111/j.1532-5415.2011.03671.x
- Lindesay, J., Rockwood, K., & Macdonald, A. (2002). *Delirium in old age*. Oxford; New York: Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press.
- Maldonado, J. R. (2013). Neuropathogenesis of delirium: Review of current etiologic theories and common pathways. *The American journal of Geriatric Psychiatry 21*(12), 1190-1222. doi:10.1016/j.jagp.2013.09.005
- Malik, A., Harlan, T., & Cobb, J. (2016). Stop. Think. Delirium! A quality improvement initiative to explore utilising a validated cognitive assessment tool in the acute inpatient medical setting to detect delirium and prompt early intervention. *Journal of Clinical Nursing, 25*(21-22), 3400-3408. doi:10.1111/jocn.13166

- Marias, Y., & Glasauer, P. (2014). *Guidelines for assessing nutrition-related knowledge, attitudes and practices: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)*.
- Mariz, J., Santos, N. C., Afonso, H., Rodrigues, P., Faria, A., Sousa, N., & Teixeira, J. (2013). Risk and clinical-outcome indicators of delirium in an emergency department intermediate care unit (EDIMCU): an observational prospective study. *Boston Medical Center Emergency Medicine, 13*(1), 2.
- McCrow, J., Sullivan, K. A., & Beattie, E. R. (2013). Delirium knowledge and recognition: A randomized controlled trial of a web-based educational intervention for acute care nurses. *Nurse Education Today*.
doi:10.1016/j.nedt.2013.12.006
- McCrow, J., Sullivan, K. A., & Beattie, E. R. (2013). Delirium knowledge and recognition: A randomized controlled trial of a web-based educational intervention for acute care nurses. *Nurse Education Today, 34*(6), 912-917.
doi:10.1016/j.nedt.2013.12.006
- McCusker, J., Cole, M. G., Dendukuri, N., & Belzile, E. (2003). Does delirium increase hospital stay? *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society, 51*(11), 1539-1546.
- Meagher, D. J., Morandi, A., Inouye, S. K., Ely, W., Adamis, D., Maclullich, A. J., . . . Trzepacz, P. T. (2014). Concordance between DSM-IV and DSM-5 criteria for delirium diagnosis in a pooled database of 768 prospectively evaluated patients using the delirium rating scale-revised-98. *BioMedical Central Medicine, 12*, 164. doi:10.1186/s12916-014-0164-8

- Mueller, G., Schumacher, P., Wetzlmier, J. Lechleitner, M., Priv.-Doz, E., (2017). Inter-Rater Reliability and User-Friendliness of the Delirium Observation Screening Scale. *Journal of Nursing Measurement,, 25(3)*, 504-518. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1891/1061-3749.25.3.504>
- Muleme, J., Kankya, C., Ssempebwa, J. C., Mazeri, S., & Muwonge, A. (2017). A framework for integrating qualitative and quantitative data in knowledge, attitude, and practice studies: A case study of pesticide usage in Eastern Uganda. *Frontiers in Public Health, 5*, 318. doi:10.3389/fpubh.2017.00318
- O'Regan, N. A., Ryan, D., Boland, E., Connolly, W., McGlade, C., Leonard, M., . . . Timmons, S. (2014). Attention! A good bedside test for delirium? . *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery & Psychiatry, 85*, 1122. doi:doi:10.1136/jnnp-2013-307053
- Rav-Marathe, K., Wan, T. T. H., & Marathe, S. (2016). A systematic review on the KAPO framework for diabetes education and research. *Medical Research Archives, 4(1)*.
- Rattanasompattikul, M., Feroze, U., Molnar, M. Z., Dukkupati, R., Kovesdy, C. P., Nissenson, A. R., Norris, K. C., Kopple, J. D., ... Kalantar-Zadeh, K. (2011). Charlson comorbidity score is a strong predictor of mortality in hemodialysis patients. *International urology and nephrology, 44(6)*, 1813-23.

- Rice, K. L., Bennett, M. J., Berger, L., Jennings, B., Eckhardt, L., Fabre-LaCoste, N., . . . Ely, E. W. (2017). A pilot randomized controlled trial of the feasibility of a multicomponent delirium prevention intervention versus usual care in acute stroke. *Journal of Cardiovascular Nursing, 32*(1), E1-e10.
doi:10.1097/jcn.0000000000000356
- Rosenbloom-Brunton, D. A., Henneman, E. A., & Inouye, S. K. (2010). Feasibility of family participation in a delirium prevention program for hospitalized older adults. *Journal of Gerontological Nursing, 36*(9), 22-33. doi:10.3928/00989134-20100330-02
- Rubin, F. H., Bellon, J., Bilderback, A., Urda, K., & Inouye, S. K. (2017). Effect of the Hospital Elder Life Program on risk of 30-day readmission. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*. doi:10.1111/jgs.15132
- Rubin, F. H., Bellon, J., Bilderback, A., Urda, K., & Inouye, S. K. (2018). Effect of the Hospital Elder Life Program on risk of 30-day r. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society, 66*(1), 145-149. doi:10.1111/jgs.15132
- Rubin, F. H., Williams, J. T., Lescisin, D. A., Mook, W. J., Hassan, S., & Inouye, S. K. (2006). Replicating the Hospital Elder Life Program in a community hospital and demonstrating effectiveness using quality improvement methodology. *Journal of American Geriatric Society, 54*. doi:10.1111/j.1532-5415.2006.00744.x
- Rynga, D., Kumar, S., Gaiind, R., & Rai, A. (2017). Hand hygiene compliance and associated factors among health care workers in a tertiary care hospital: Self-reported behaviour and direct observation. *International Journal of Infection Control, 13*(i 1). doi:10.3396/IJIC.v13i1.002.17

- Siddiqi, N., Harrison, J. K., Clegg, A., Teale, E. A., Young, J., Taylor, J., & Simpkins, S. A. (2016). Interventions for preventing delirium in hospitalised non-ICU patients. *Cochrane Database Systemic Review*, 3, Cd005563. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD005563.pub3
- Siddiqi, N., Stockdale, R., Britton, A. M., & Holmes, J. (2007). Interventions for preventing delirium in hospitalised patients. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*, 18.
- Stegg, L., Langelaan, M., Ijkema, R., Nugus, P., & Wagner, C. (2014). Improving delirium care for hospitalized older patients. A qualitative study identifying barriers to guideline adherence. *Journal of Evaluation in Clinical Practice*, 20(6), 813-819. doi:10.1111/jep.12229
- Steunenberg, B., van der Mast, R., Strijbos, M. J., Inouye, S. K., & Schuurmans, M. J. (2016). How trained volunteers can improve the quality of hospital care for older patients. A qualitative evaluation within the Hospital Elder Life Program (HELP). *Geriatric Nursing*, 37(6), 458-463. doi:10.1016/j.gerinurse.2016.06.014
- Sullivan, D., Regan, N. A., & Timmons, S. (2016). Validity and Reliability of the 6-Item Cognitive Impairment Test for Screening Cognitive Impairment: A Review. *Dementia and geriatric cognitive disorders*, 42(1-2), 42. doi:10.1159/000448241
- Tauro, R. (2014). Delirium awareness – Improving recognition and management through education and use of a care pathway. *BioMedical Journal of Quality Improvement Reports*, 2(2), u203195.w201451. doi:10.1136/bmjquality.u203195.w1451

- van Velthuisen, E. L., Zwakhalen, S. M., Mulder, W. J., Verhey, F. R., & Kempen, G. I. (2017). Detection and management of hyperactive and hypoactive delirium in older patients during hospitalization: a retrospective cohort study evaluating daily practice. *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*. doi:10.1002/gps.4690
- Wagner, C. (2015). American Geriatrics Society abstracted clinical practice guideline for postoperative delirium in older adults. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 63(1), 142-150. doi:10.1111/jgs.13281
- Xu, W., Sun, G., Lin, Z., Chen, M., Yang, B., Chen, H., & Cao, K. (2010). Knowledge, attitude, and behavior in patients with atrial fibrillation undergoing radiofrequency catheter ablation. *Journal of Interventional Cardiac Electrophysiology*, 28(3), 199-207. doi:10.1007/s10840-010-9496-2
- Yanamadala, M., Wieland, D., & Heflin, M. T. (2013). Educational interventions to improve recognition of delirium: a systematic review. *Journal of American Geriatric Society*, 61(11), 1983-1993. doi:10.1111/jgs.12522
- Young, J., Murthy, L., Westby, M., Akunne, A., & O'Mahony, R. (2010). Diagnosis, prevention, and management of delirium: Summary of NICE guidance. *British Medical Journal*, 341, c3704. doi:10.1136/bmj.c3704
- Yue, J., Tabloski, P., Dowal, S. L., Puelle, M. R., Nandan, R., & Inouye, S. K. (2014). NICE to HELP: Operationalizing national institute for health and clinical excellence guidelines to improve clinical practice. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 62(4), 754-761. doi:10.1111/jgs.12768

APPENDIX A

LIST OF VARIABLES USED IN THE STUDY

Variables	Type
Age	Continuous
Gender (Male/Female)	Ordinal
Living Status (Home vs. Nursing Home, ICU, & Transfer to another hospital)	Ordinal
Length of stay	Continuous
Discharge Disposition (home vs. Nursing home)	Ordinal
Function at home (Day 0)	Continuous
Function Day 1	Continuous
Function Day 2	Continuous
Function Day 3	Continuous
Use of Sitter (Yes/ No)	Ordinal
Use of Restraints (Yes/ No)	Ordinal
Nurse Observed delirium (Y/N)	Ordinal
Altered level of Conscious in ED (Y/N)	Ordinal
Fall before Admission (Y/N)	Ordinal
MOTYB Day 1 (pass: No, no-pass: Yes)	Ordinal
CAM-ICU Day 1 (negative: N, positive: Y)	Ordinal
MOTYB Day 2 (pass: No, no-pass: Yes)	Ordinal
CAM-ICU Day 2 (negative: N, positive: Y)	Ordinal
MOTYB Day 3 (pass: No, no-pass: Yes)	Ordinal
CAM-ICU Day 3 (negative: N, positive: Y)	Ordinal
Charlson Comorbidity Index	Continuous
Medical records were reviewed for documentation on delirium, altered mental status, medication list, and past medical history as part of baseline assessment.	

APPENDIX B

TABLE OF DELIRIUM SCREENING TOOLS

Delirium Screening Tools

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/measures	Findings	Conclusion/ notes
a-Identify the accuracy of screening tools for frailty older adult using(VMS) b- feasibility to predict adverse outcomes. c- literatures review to increase predictive power of screening algorithm (Heim et al., 2015).	Prospective cohort study ($n = 883$, control $n = 812$) - 4 hospitals in Netherlands. - Pt age ≥ 70 , elective/ acutely hospitalized. -screening tools: VMS, 6-item cognitive impairment test, & mini mental, ADL→ Katz index, fall risk: simple yes/no Q, under nourished: weight loss, Del: answer yes to one of three Q: memory problem, need help with selfcare, & previous confusion. ISAR: ED tool, 6CIT, MMSE Candidate inclusion for prediction model was based on 3-month follow up.	RN interviewed pts at admission, 3 & 12 months after a self-administered questionnaire measure level of function.	% of pts who scored +frailty: 13 - 72%. Sensitivity of the test: 24 - 89%, specificity:35 - 91%	Age and two Positive predictors in VMS = strongest prediction of adverse outcome with PPV: 50% in three-month/ 44% in 12-month & NPV: 86 % & 86% accordingly. This study enhanced the face validity of VMS. It is feasible to implement My notes: VMS evaluates pts for undernutrition, fall, ADL limitation & Del.
a-Del incidence & its outcomes b-To ↑ awareness of Del. in health care system c- Identify Del. risk factors to improve	Prospective observational study. -Two internal medicine wards in university affiliated public hospitals Florence, Italy. $n = 560$	RN/MD screen pts using: -SPMSQ & CAM. LOS, DC destination, comorbidities, demographics.	63 Del. cases, 44(8%) incidence cases, 19 (3%) prevalence. 32 hyperactive, 5 hypoactive, 7 mixed. 34 (77%) had precipitating factors, 38% sepsis, 18% pain, 9% dehydration or electrolyte imbalance. Hyperactive & mixed	11% of older hospitalized had Del. (8%) incidence. DM and renal failure are the major risk factors associated to Del incidence. Despite staff education

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/measures	Findings	Conclusion/ notes
definition of high risk pts (Fortini et al., 2014)	IC: age $\geq 65+$, screened in first 24 h of admission. EC: positive CAM in admission. Over two months.		were treated with meds (77%). 5% of them restraint. No meds for hypoactive. Risk factors: SPMSQ ≥ 3 (46%, $p = .0002$), DM, chronic kidney failure & male, # of home meds. There is association between SPMSQ score & Del ($p = .0003$, $OR 1.260$). Incidence of Del \downarrow DC home ($p = .01$, $OR 0.428$). + incidence & prevalence of Del = transfer to nursing home/subacute care ($p < .01$ $OR 3.026$). No difference in mortality OR /transfer other units	there was unrec. cases (no # provided).
a-Evaluate need for assessment tool b-algorithm to improve Del detection, c- evaluate feasibility of new algorithm (Grossmann et al., 2014)	Pre-posttest with two data collections/ cross sectional design used posttest/combine pre/post data sets. ED university hospital Switzerland. IC: all Pt ≥ 65 , EC: resuscitation room, DC in two hours, insufficient German Language /aphasic/coma $n = 207$, 74 pre-test, 133 post-test	mCAM-ED & MSQ by ED RN. during pretest, RA & RN assessed pts. Comparing the result the pretest eval. Was done (6 days). Demographic data, # of meds, age adjusted Charlson comorbidity index, exposure to anticholinergics. Interview for informal detection of Del. confirmation of Del. by MD/if not the RA result was definite. Feasibility: RN adherence of algorithm (by completing screening	Prevalence in pre 16.4% & post 5.5% ($p = .021$). Total prevalence rate in ED 9.5%. difference between sensitivity and specificity significant for nurses informal rating ($p = .012$). Adherence rate = 76.5% screening sheet analyze: 8.1 % was not conclusive.	The study confirmed the need for standardized method. High adherence & feasibility of algorithm. Limit: specificity and sensitivity of mCAM-ED was not evaluated (small n).

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/measures	Findings	Conclusion/ notes
		sheet)/ ability to perform mCAM-ED (investigator review the RN assessment)		
To evaluate the sensitivity and specificity of 2-step asses tools among ED pts ≥ 65 , using Psychiatrist's assessment as the reference standardspace(Han et al., 2013)	Tertiary care academic ED. Convenient sampling ($n= 406$). IC: ≥ 65 , in ED <12 h. not in hallway bed. English speaking, EC: deaf, blind, already enrolled, comatose, unable to follow command, left ER before study completed. MD vs. RA performing the eval.	Tools: DTS, bCAM, combine DTS+ bCAM assessment was performed by MD, or RA	50/406 had Del. in ED based reference. DTS: 98% S & Sp 55% (95 % <i>CI</i>). Negative likelihood =0.04 (for both rater) bCAM, Sp: 95.8% (MD) & 96.9% (RA). S: 84% (MD) 78% (RA). Positive likelihood ratio 19.9 (MD) & 25.2 (RA). DTS followed by bCAM: S 84% & Sp 95.8%. RA performed both steps: S 78% & Sp 97.2%. IF MD performed both steps: S 82% & Sp 95.8 %	2-step tool is reliable and valid. It is short and quickly can be performed by any healthcare provider regardless their background. Many limitations mentioned. One center, potential biased, discordance, accuracy not checked in not RA setting. A negative DTS can 50% \downarrow Del. asses. Need. bCAM take < 1 mints. Appropriate for ED, though not comprehensive as CAM (CAM S: 93% & Sp: 86%)
To answer these Qs: a- Evaluate Del. Asses. Tool used in ED& out of hospital? b- evaluate validated screening tools to use for elderly ED pts? c-find evidence when screening should be performed in ED? (LaMantia et al., 2014)	systemic review among articles ($n = 22$) who studied ED or out of hospital (EMS). pts ≥ 65 . IC: asses of mental status for Del. EC: eval performed outside ED/EMS, pt who is delirious result of meds, or alcohol, non-English articles, non-relevant subjects, not peer reviewed, or conference presentation	From 1946: MEDLINE/EMBASE, from 1941-2013 from 1941-2013: Cochrane Library, PsycINFO, and CINAHL from 1965. Terms: Del, "acute confusion state" and emergency, ER, ED. 2 reviews \rightarrow abstract \rightarrow 22 was chosen for eval	All articles addressed use of screening tool within ED, 3 /22 \rightarrow optimal timing of screening process in ED. 2 \rightarrow validation study of tools & 20 \rightarrow appilcation of screening tools. Del was identified in ED pts with 7 different tools: CAM, CAM-ICU, CAM-ED, Original Brain Syndrome Scale, DX and Statistical Manual criteria, Del. Rating Scale & NEECHAM Confusion scale. Only CAM validated for elderly asses in Ed. 3-	There is lack of asses. tools that validated only for ED. Older ED pts frequently are Del.& rec. of Del has not improved among ED providers. it is possible not proven Del goes unrec, due to lack of validated and brief tool & lack of provider rec. of provider of potential consequence of Del. screening at multiple point of ED visit may \uparrow identification. effectiveness of the tools in

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/measures	Findings	Conclusion/ notes
			4 hours interval reported in three studies	daily clinical use yet to be demonstrated.
a- description of psychometric analysis of Del asses tools used in ICU PAD Guidelines. b-to performed an updates psychometric analysis on Del. asses tools based on recent evidence to guide professional team in the selection of the optimal tool to use in daily practice (Gelinas et al., 2018)	Systemic review. Search criteria; development, validation, and/or implementation of Del. asses tools in adult ICU pt. all publications between 1996-2014, $n = 36$. studies referred to 5 ICU Del asses tools, 20 referred to ICU PAD, 15 →analyzed 2 or more tools. IC: English articles, adults ≥ 18 , sample size ≥ 30 . EC: abstracts, editorial, narrative reviews, case reports, letter to the editor	Scale development, validity, feasibility, clinical relevant of tools were analyzed based on psychometric scoring system for Del. asses tools.	24 → CAM ICU, 10→ intensive care Del screening checklist, 3→ Nursing Del. screening scale, 2→Del detection score, 2→ cognitive test for Del. 4→adressed 2 or more tools. Weighted score CAM ICU→19.6 (weighted score 0 -20), ICDSC (19.2) these two indicated very good psychometric properties. NuDESC→13.6 moderate score (S & Sp > 80%), DDS→11.2 low score (S 30% Sp 91%), CTD→8.2 very low score (S 94.7% Sp 98.8 %). In most study S of CAM reported 47-100% and Sp 81-100%. It is feasible (30 min to teach). ICDSC →feasible. NuDESC → feasibility has not reported. CTD not have prospective validation testing. Not recommended. DDS is a poor tool. NuDESC validation was supported with S & Sp but it is not validated for ICU.	CAM ICU & ICDSC are the most reliable tools for Del. screening in adult ICU pts. These tools translated to different languages with similar findings to the original language. NuDESC has not translated to English yet. Two other systemic review agreed with this finding: CAM ICU and ICDSC are the most S & Sp tools
a-To investigate performance of mCAM-ED compared to resent DSM-IV-TR, b- The mCAM-ED ability to identify Del in older	Single prospective validation study. Tertiary university hospital ED in Switzerland. Data collected 24 h/ day x 11 day ($n = 286$).	2 steps to reduce length: a- screen for inattention, b- mCAM-ED to assess Del. uses MBT. mCAM-ED uses kahn et al. (1960) MSQ. MSQ→10 items (time, place,	trained RN complete m-CAM-ED, in an h, geriatrician performed reference standard Del, asses. Time documented. S, Sp, +/-likelihood & two-sided <i>CI</i> (95%) Were analyzed. Del prevalence = 7%. MBT → S 0.95 & Sp 0.86. +	mCam-ED has good S & Sp. This tool identifies Del. efficiently in minimum time. Sp mCAM-ED in dementia pt is moderate.

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/measures	Findings	Conclusion/ notes
ED pts w/wo dementia c- eval. efficiency of tool to keep screen time short (Hasemann et al., 2017).	IC: age \geq 65 ED visit. EC: resuscitation, admit to ICU, emergency surgery, language barrier, sever hearing impairment, coma	person, memory) 2 < errors = problem. Fluctuation, hyperalert, drowsiness was observed during interview. Other variables: demographic data, chief complain, Charlson comorbidity index, dementia	predict value 0.34, negative predict value 1.00, - likelihood 0.06, positive likelihood 6.83. S \uparrow in pt wo Dementia. mCAM-ED \rightarrow S 0.9, Sp 0.98, + predict value 0.75, - predict value 0.99. + likelihood 39.9, - likelihood 0.1.S does not change w/wo dementia ($p = 1.000$) Sp has significant difference w/wo ($p = .002$) MBT took 30 seconds & mCAM-ED took 3.2 min (SD 2.0) in pt wo dementia & over 5.6 (SD 3.2) for pt w dementia.	This study reference Grossmann (2014) algorithm as guide to screen pts. References are old.
To identify, compare, and evaluate validation studies of Del screening tools inpatient (De & Wand, 2015)	systemic review. MEDLINE, CINAHL (1996-2014) & PsychInfo (1987-2014) searched. terms: Del & screening NOT intensive care unit (ICU), Del & rating scale NOT ICU, Del AND tool NOT ICU, Del & validation NOT ICU. IC: used ICD & DSM criteria, hospitalized adult, evaluate cognitive eval. Tool, EC: solely concerns rating Del severity (over identification), not used DSM or ICD, validate a non-English version of	Quality of study assessed using STARD (scored 1-25 & score $>20 =$ high quality)	21 tools validated. Most common, CAM, brief CAM, CAM-ICU (13). Then DRS& DRS-R-98(6). 66% of studies included dementia pts. 4 studies included nonnative language pt to the screening. 83 % = \uparrow quality, 43% not reported time between reference assessment & the tool & not reported interval between assessments. DSM/ICD raters include registrars, geriatricians, psychiatrist, or neurologists where reference standard was carried. DRS \rightarrow 82% S & 94 Sp (a good S & Sp). DRS-R-98 \rightarrow poor -moderate S & Sp (75%). CAM \rightarrow S& Sp $> 95\%$. Similar result in combination of CAM with DSI. DDT-pro has	CAM has good S & Sp in ED, Post-Operative & mixed inpatients settings. DRS/DRS-98 has better result in psychogeriatric population. 4ATs good S & Sp in mixed inpatient /geriatrics. confirmed CAM is widely used instrument.

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/measures	Findings	Conclusion/ notes
	Del tool, Del in community <i>n</i> = 31		excellent S & Sp (100% & 94%) tested small group of brain injury pt. this tool correlate well with DRS. MDSA is tested small group & limited in generalizability. SQEEC ask pt to describe a narrative, with S & SP (good, 83% & 81%), excluded people with ↓LOC. 4AT→ good S & Sp (90% & 84%) it is easy to use and rapid to use, help to assess fluctuation of LOC & hypoactive. DOSS, S & Sp is not reported against standard and validated in small sample size. 4 items extracted from InterRAI to develop tool→ need more study to eval.	
To investigate the performance of the mRASS in detecting Del in ED older pts w/wo dementia(Grossmann et al., 2017)	sub analysis of prospective trial performed to eval CAM-ED. Intended sample size (<i>n</i> = 492) collected through consecutive sampling of Ed pts age ≥ 65 during 11-day period.	mRASS scale ranges from -5 to +4. Value difference from 0 defined as indicator of Del. applied by trained RN. Compared to the DSM-IV-TR.	<i>n</i> = 285, Del prevalence (7%), S & Sp 0.7 & 0.93, PPV 0.4, NPV 0.98, LR+ 10.3, LR- 0.3; In <i>n</i> = 41 Del prevalence (26.8%) S & Sp 0.55 & 0.83, PPV 0.55, NPV 0.83, LR+ 3.27, LR-0.55. In <i>n</i> = 244 Del prevalence 3.6%, S & Sp 0.89 & 0.94, PPV 0.38, NPV 1.00, LR+ 16.07, LR- 0.12.	mRASS by itself is not sufficient tool. it has good Sp and weak S for Del pts w/wo dementia. combination of other tools looks necessary. mRASS had different finding in other reported studies. In one ED study S & SP 0.84 & 0.88 which might be related to heterogeneity of sampling & setting.
To determine inter-agreement and inter-rater reliability of DOSS (Mueller, 2017)	Quantitative descriptive cross-sectional study. with 2 convenient (<i>n</i> = 141 patients and <i>n</i> = 36 RN) MMSE score > 20,	RN trained to use DOSS. DOSS to be conducted in 1h of the admission. Two RN independently screen each pt q 24 h. x	Rater agreement of total Del: Day 1: <i>n</i> = 140, Pa 79.9%, Pe 73.6% <i>K</i> = 0.214 (<i>CI</i> 95% [0.065 - 0.363]), ICC 0.535 (<i>CI</i> 95%, [0.406 - 0.643]).	Inter-rater agreement of DOSS is acceptable. Overall agreement between two RNs high. Though Kappa showed poor to fair agreement, ICC

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/measures	Findings	Conclusion/ notes
	EC: dementia, Del at admission.	2 days. 3 open ended questions about strength, weakness & implementation of DOSS in nursing practice was added. Raters were blinded of other raters' findings.	Day 2: $n = 140$, Pa 78.5%, Pe 73.8%, $K = 0.181$ (CI 95% [0.233 - 0.516]). user friendly: 11.19 ($SD \pm 7.254$) rating were completed. 18% screened, 3 min, 29% $3 < \text{time} < 6$ min, 11% $7 < \text{time} < 11$ min & 22% $\text{time} > 10$ mins	showed moderate agreement. Interrater agreement risk category showed similar result on item level and total score. User friendly of DOSS showed in homogeneous results. Limitations: sample size, observer bias, method that data collected q 24 h
To eval. DX accuracy of CAM-ICU & ICDSC in mixed ICU patients among nursing and medical staff (Barman et al., 2018).	Prospective cohort study. ICU in India. IC: ventilated/non-ventilated pts, been in ICU for 24h, Gloss coma < 9 , RASS ≤ -3 . EC: sever dementia, psychosis, progressed neurological diseases, readmission. $n = 310$ evaluated over one year.	Demographic data, DX at admission, Benzo usage, duration of ventilator use, blood urea, creatinine, & bilirubin was collect. Del asses. Conducted by RN an intensivist separately by using CAM-ICU and ICDSC tools. A psychiatrist evaluated all pts based on DSM-IV. Investigators were blinded of pts' Dx, labs, or other raters' findings.	As DSM eval. Del prevalence = 45%. Del pts were sicker than average ($\pm 2 \times SD$). Inter-rater agreement for CAM-ICU: ($K = 0.86$ (CI 95% [90.83-90.96])). Inter-rater-for ICDSC ($K = 77.8\%$ (CI 95% [62.9-88.8])). CAM-ICU DOR = 86.1 & ICDSC DOR = 36.9. DOR (Intensivist) $>$ DOR RN (120 & 67 CAM-ICU & 53 & 27 \rightarrow ICDSC). S CAM-ICU $>$ ICDSC (84% vs 77%).	High Kappa agreement found between RN & intensivist. (0.84) & between 2 RNs ($K = 0.95$). CAM-ICU \rightarrow better tool. The assessment results between intensivist & RN were comparable and similar to reference.
a-To conduct a comparative study & hypothesize 3D-CAM is more appropriate for medical units compare to CAM-	cross sectional comparative effectiveness study. two medical units of a university affiliated hospital in Boston. $n = 201$ IC: age > 75 , admit to general medical unit, able	Reference eval: 45mints comprehensive interview/ proxy- based screening (for base line dementia), AD-8, GDS-SF, MCI MoCA, Charlson index. Final DX were adjusted with	Mean age = 84, 52% Charlson ≥ 3 , 26% dementia, 24% depression. 3D-CAM (3 min) & CAM-ICU (4 min). Pt with dementia both tools 5 min. 19 % (19 pts) DX Del base on reference. 3D-CAM identified 24 pts (24%) & CAM-ICU 10(10 %). S & Sp for 3-D CAM 95% & 93 %	S (3D-CAM) $>$ S (CAM-ICU). Sp 3D-CAM $>$ Sp CAM-ICU in dementia pt. 3D-Cam has easier algorithm \rightarrow training easier

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/measures	Findings	Conclusion/ notes
ICU (Kuczmaraska et al., 2016)	to communicate in English, no terminal condition, expect LOS > 2 days, not previous study participant	clinical panel and determined based on DSM-IV. geropsychiatric randomly selected 2 equal # cases, 10w Del & 10 wo Del. at this level CAM-ICU & 3D-Cam were administered. All 3 asses in first 24h.	and CAM-ICU 53% & 100%. On dementia pts S & sp for 3D-CAM 92% & 77% & CAM-ICU 62% & 100	

Note. Admit, admission; AD-8, Alzheimer disease 8; Asses, assessment; CAM, confusion assessment method (HELP delirium assessment tool); bCAM, brief confusion assessment method; CAC, clinical assessment of confusion; CI, confidence interval; CTD, cognitive test for delirium; 6CIT, 6-item cognitive impairment test; DDS, delirium detection score; Dx, diagnosis; DRS, delirium rating scale; DOSS, delirium observation screening scale; DOR, diagnostic odds ratio; DRS-R-98, revised version of DRS; DST, digit span test; DC, discharge; DSI, delirium symptom index; Del, Delirium; DM, diabetes mellitus; DSM, diagnostic and statistical manual; DSM-IV-TR, diagnostic and statistical manual-fourth edition-text revision; DTS, delirium triage screen; 4AT, 4 A's test- a delirium assessment tool; ED/ER, Emergency department/room; eval, evaluation; EC, Excluding Criteria; EMS, emergency medical services; GDS-SF, geriatric depression scale-short; h, hour; ICC, intraclass correlation coefficient; ICD, international classification for diseases; ICDSC, intensive care delirium screening checklist; ICU, Intensive care unit; IC, Including Criteria; ISAR, identification of senior at risk; LR+: positive likelihood; LR-, negative likelihood, LOS, length of stay; MDSA, memorial delirium assessment scale; mCAM-ED: modified confusion assessment method- emergency department; MSQ, mental status questionnaire; MMSE, mini mental state examination; MD, physician; MIC, mild cognitive impairment; med.rec, medical record; meds, medications; MoCA, Montreal cognitive assessment; rec, recognized/recognition; Mints, minuets; MBT, month backward test; NuDESC, Nurse delirium screening scale; NVP, negative -predicted value; n, sample size; OR, odd ratio; RA, research assistant; RN, registered nurse; Unrec, unrecognized; mRASS, modified Richmond agitation sedation scale; Pa, overall percent agreement; Pe, Chance-agreement probability; PPV, positive-predicted value; PAD, pain agitation delirium; Q, question; STARD, standards for reporting of diagnostic accuracy; SPMSQ, short portable mental status questionnaire; S, sensitivity; SD, standard deviation; SPMSQ, short portable mental status questionnaire; SP, specificity VMS, Dutch Safety Management Program= *VeiligheidsManagementSysteem*; W/Wo, with and without; →, to, had; & , and; ≥, greater and equal; ≤, less and equal; %, percentage; ↑, increase;

APPENDIX C

TABLE OF DELIRIUM SCREENING STUDIES

Delirium Screening Studies

Purpose	Design variables/sample/setting	Methods/Measure	Findings	Conclusion/Limitations& notes
<p>a-To determine the incidence of Del in ED pt age ≥ 65 in ED > 12h.</p> <p>b- to evaluate the impact of ED associated del of LOS in hospital (Emond et al., 2017).</p>	<p>Retrospective cohort study. pts admitted to university hospital in Québec between 2009-2011 ($n = 200$). IC: age ≥ 65, non-Del. at admission, ED stay minimum 12 h, admit to any hospital unit. EC: resident of long-term facilities, Hx dementia, psychiatric conditions.</p>	<p>Del & LOS collected using administrative benchmarks. Demographic data, ED LOS & hospital LOS, Charlson comorbidity index, # of meds in ED stay (Beers criteria) & main DX during hospitalization were collected. Del asses. Performed based on CAM chart-based method.</p>	<p>18% ($n = 36$) of pts =Del. 50% of this group = Del in the first 24 h. 41.2% episodes started when pt was still in ED. Age distribution: 13 % (5 pts) age = 65-74, 50% (18 pts) age = 75-84 & 37% (13 pts) = ≥ 85. Pt with = Del had > ED LOS ($p > .05$). Pt with +ED stay Del had received more opioid-related meds. The median hospital LOS \uparrow with incident of ED Del. (10.2 days \rightarrow 17.9 days) ($p < .05$).</p>	<p>Long ED stay > 12h strong independent predictor for Del. Study did not eval. Impact of Del. on overall hospital LOS.</p> <p>Note: CAM chart based has 74% S & 83% Sp (Inouye et al., 2005).</p>
<p>To measure prevalence and incidence of delirium in ED (Hsieh et al., 2015)</p>	<p>Prospective cohort study, tertiary hospital New York. ED pt age ≥ 65 were screened ($n = 260$). EC: admit ED to ICU, non-English speaking, coma, sever dementia, sever psychiatric illness, or pt eloped. Covariable: age education & home meds.</p>	<p>CAM-ICU, RASS, MIS, IQCODE (if pt was Del). KATZ, Charlson comorbidity index, and REMS & clinical outcomes. Asses performed once daily on the first 3 days (ED = day 1). Del. binary, categorical & exploratory analysis done for. Data collected on covariables.</p>	<p>29 pt Del + in ER. 15/29 Del + were not dx in ER (52%). Del resolved by day 2 in 28 % ($n = 8$) & by day 3 in 21% ($n = 6$). Del persist in 2 days in 52% ($n = 15$). 9 pt no Del day 1 \rightarrow Del+ day 2 ($n = 4$) & day 3 ($n = 5$). Del+ in 3 days of admission \rightarrow \uparrow ICU admit & in hospital death (OR 8.07, $p = .005$. Del within the first 3 day was not</p>	<p>Del persist in $\frac{3}{4}$ of pt from ED to inpatient. Early dx of Del is useful for short-term hospital outcome. Possible explanation of Del poor outcome is Del incidences were missed</p> <p>Note: only study so far that examined prevalence and outcome of Del in ED and inpatient units. This study</p>

Purpose	Design variables/sample/setting	Methods/Measure	Findings	Conclusion/Limitations& notes
			significantly related to decline at dc ($p = .08$). Del persist from ED to hospital↑ decline at the DC ($p = .012$).	does not show relation between Del and deliriogenic meds.
a-To determine how often Del. missed in ER, and if hospitalist can DX at admit. b- Identify Del. risk factors in ER c-characterize Del. subtypes in ER (Han et al., 2009).	Cross-sectional convenient sampling ($n = 303$), Tertiary care academic EDEC: refused consent, previously enrolled, non-English speaking, dementia, unarousable to verbal stimuli IC: English speaking 65 + for <12 h.	Used: CAM-ICU to assess Del., Richmond agitation & sedation scale. →classify Del. psychomotor subtypes. DX by ER MD/ hospital MD eval. By medrec. review	8.3% ER admit. →Del. at admit 92%,95% <i>CI</i> [74 - 99.0%]). →Hypoactive Psychomotor subtype. 19/25 (76%, 95% <i>CI</i> [54.9% -90.6%]). → not rec. by ER MD 15 (93.8%- 95% <i>CI</i> [69.8- 99.8]) unrec. By Hospitalist at the time of admission. Dementia, Katz ADL ≤ 4 & hearing impairment ($p < .001$).	Del. commonly occurs in ER. Most of them hypoactive.76% of cases ER MD missed to DX del. if ER MD miss. →hospitalist nearly always missed to dx (only 6.3% dx, 90% missed). Using DX risk score. →improve Del. screening efficiency in ER. The absence of routine Del. screening in ED is the cause of under dx of Del. in ED. Del. Subtypes risk factors: Dementia, Katz ADL ≤ 4 & hearing impairment, and ED diagnosed infection. Limitation: interviewing ER MD, or their awareness may increase the absolute DX
a-To analyze how often Del subtypes (hyper/hypo) were recognized and reported in daily hospital routine	A retrospective cohort study. 715 beds University hospital, Netherlands. Psychiatric &geriatrics wards. IC: Pts age ≥ 65, admitted between January -December 2014 ($n =$	Demographic data, duration of Del, Del transient, Del obs. Score < 3in three consecutive remeasurements, pt's died or Dc, Del management (pharmacological/non-pharmacological/psychosocial),	Overall baseline characteristic for subtypes → no difference ($p = .16 - .59$). main admission cause: cardiovascular 92%). most commonly cause of Del = Infection & surgery (38% &	Del was confirmed in 401 pts (5%) of admission. 307 (77%)hyperactive, & 94 pts (23%) hypoactive. Del is under- recognized /reported (especially hypoactive). Low Del detection can be

Purpose	Design variables/sample/setting	Methods/Measure	Findings	Conclusion/Limitations& notes
b-Identify potential differences in management of Del subtypes. C-report adverse outcomes of both patients' groups(van Velthuijsen et al., 2017)	7,907) 401 of them was DX as Del by MD or NP or Del at dc time.	adverse outcomes (LOS, Mortality, DC destination). Pts medical records	24%). 30% → no direct cause. Management: 86% received meds (specially Haldol). Hyperactive received ↑meds (89% 77% $p = .004$). No significant difference among other interventions subgroups (reorientation, consults, restrains, meds & reorientation, & no intervention). In hospital death ↑for Hypoactive ($p = .012$); the rest outcomes→ no difference	cause of no difference among outcomes. 90% received meds → need promotion of non-pharmacological interventions. Note: Mixed Del considered Hyperactive. If no subtype recorded the author judged it based on report. Dc destination: only for pts came from Home
To explore the relationship between Del and pts' outcomes after DC (Mariz et al., 2013).	A prospective (4 months) cohort study data collected on all admission. ($n = 238$). EDIMCU unit in a tertiary care university hospital in Braga, Portugal. IC: age ≥ 18 , admitted for > 24 h to EDIMCU. EC: screening was not performed for any reasons: refusal, coma, communication barrier, dementia or neuropsychiatric problems, and unable to follow command.	CAM-ICU & RASS tool were used to screen pts, A month after outcome data collected with review pt's electronic medical records or by phone interview. Data collection q 12 h., starting in the first 12 h of admission. Screening performed by staff RN (all trained). Demographic data, Charlson comorbidity index, blood analysis, admission dx, SIRS.	20% of pts ($n = 57$) →Del, 79.9 % no Del ($n = 226$). 68% of Del →Dx in the first 24h. 22.8% → 24 < DX >72 h; 8.8 %→ DX after 72h. 56% ($n = 32$) → Del for 1 day, 24% ($n = 14$) →Del 2 days, 12.3% ($n = 7$)→ Del for 3 days, 5.3%($n = 3$) → Del 4 days & 1case →Del for 6 days. Del pts: older (mean 67.1 vs. 60.2 $p < .006$), ↑ SIRS (38.6% vs. 23.4%, $p < .028$), ↑Charlson (4 vs.3 $p < .039$). Mixed Del had longer Del status ($p < .001$) & longer LOS ($p < .009$). LOS > Del ($p < .001$).	Del prevalence = 20.1%, Los, readmission and mortality ↑ among Del pts; majority of Del occurs in the first 24 h (importance of early screening).

Purpose	Design variables/sample/setting	Methods/Measure	Findings	Conclusion/Limitations& notes
			one moth outcome: death among Del vs. non-Del (30 % vs.10% $p < .001$).	
To determine if Del in ED prolongs LOS in hospital(Han et al., 2011)	Cohort study. Tertiary university hospital ED.U.S. Between May 2007-August 2008, convenient sampling. $n=628$. IC: English speaking, no coma, consented, age ≥ 65 , ED time $< 12h$. EC: previously enrolled, unable to follow simple command, sever dementia	Trained RA conducted: CAM-ICU, MMSE, Katz ADL, + Dementia if one of 3 +: + Hx, MMSE <24 or IQCODE > 3.38 . APACHE II, if pt had surgery	Out of 628, 17.2 % ($n = 108$) were Del.& 55.9% ($n = 351$) were admitted. 2/4 patients ($<1\%$) died in ED were Del, 26.6% ($n = 29$) of Del pts DC home form ED. The mean LOS for Del pts = 4 days & non-Del = 2.5 days ($p = .001$). HR of Del in ED was 0.71(95% CI [0.57-0.89]) after adjusted the independent variables. (HR $< 1 =$ significant)	Del in ED is an independent predictor of LOS. Del in ED \uparrow adverse outcomes. Note: S & p of CAM-ICU reported 93% & 89% with interrater reliability $K = 0.84 - 0.96$.
a-Is Del independent predictor of 6-month mortality in ED pts regardless their admission status. b-is ED Del and mortality rate modified by nursing home residence (Han et al., 2010).	Prospective cohort study in ED (Part of another study), U.S. $n = 628$ English speaking, no coma, consented, age ≥ 65 , ED time $< 12h$. EC: previously enrolled, unable to follow simple command, sever dementia	Trained RA conducted: CAM-ICU, MMSE, Katz ADL, + Dementia if one of 3 +: + Hx, MMSE < 24 or IQCODE > 3.38 . APACHE II, if pt had surgery. Outcome measurement: medical record search, social security death index,	351/628 (55.9%) admitted to hospital, 9.2 % ($n = 58$) were from nursing home, 17.2% ($n = 108$) \rightarrow Del & 12.9 % ($n = 81$) died within 6 months. 37% of Del pt died in 6 months vs 14.3% non-Del. nursing home resident Del mortality in 6 months $>$ non-Del (45.8 % vs. 26.5%).	Relationship between ED Del & 6 moth mortality. Nursing home & Del not a modifier for 6 months death ($p = .86$). Limitation: CAM-ICU only conducted at the time of enrollment.
To identify the prevalence of Del and MD Dx rate of	Systemic review articles ($n = 13$)	Databases: Medline, EMBASE, PsychINFO & CINAHL. 12 studies elder pts, one study adults.	S & Sp varies among studies. Wong et al. (2010) reported higher positive	The prevalence of Del in articles varies between 20-70 % among elderly.

Purpose	Design variables/sample/setting	Methods/Measure	Findings	Conclusion/Limitations& notes
Del in ED (Barron & Holmes, 2013) .	IC: cohort, cross sectional, ED pts in hospitals, EC: hospice, community, retrospective studies that fail to DX 2/3 of Del pts, Del treatment.	4 used CAM-ICU, one used Del rating scale, and 8 used CAM.	likelihood ratio if MD conducted the CAM. No MDs ED trained. 12 studies used CAM and CAM-ICU reported differentiate between dementia & Del. Three studies used IQCODE & MMSE to identify Del. none of these validated for ED. Ramirez-Bermudez (2006): DRS known & validated to differentiate between Del, dementia & psychosis. Comorbidity not reported in all studies, reported results heterogenous. Del DX rate for MD (8 studies): 11–46%	Many studies used convenient sampling based on availability of researcher that limited the true prevalence of Del in ED. Note: the review acknowledge CAM reliability reported in inpt setting and respectively try to evaluate studies' findings in ED compare to inpt. Studies that published after this review also has record of using IQCODE & MMSE but none talked about validating the too for ED use

Note. APACHE II, acute physiology and chronic health evaluation; Asses, assessment; CAM, confusion assessment method; CAM-ICU, modified version of confusion assessment method (CAM) uses in intensive care unit; DX, diagnosis; DC, discharge; Del, Delirium, delirious; DRS, Delirium rating scale; EC, excluding criteria; Eval, evaluation/evaluate; ED, emergency department; EDIMCU, intermediate care unit; HR, hazard ratio; Hx, history; IC, including criteria; IQCODE, informant questionnaire on cognitive decline in the elderly; KATZ, baseline function test; Katz ADL, Katz activity of daily living; LOS, length of stay; #, number; MMSE, mini-mental state examination; Meds, medication; medrec, medical record; h, hour/ hours; → had, resulted; ↑, higher, greater, increase; inpt, inpatient; MD, medical doctor; Meds: medications; Pt (s)/Pt (s), patient(s); RA, research assistant; RASS, Richmond agitation and sedation scale; REMS, baseline cognitive and functional statement; SIRS, systemic inflammatory response syndrome; U.S, United States

APPENDIX D

TABLE OF STAFF KNOWLEDGE

Staff Knowledge

Purpose	Design/variables/sample/setting	Methods/Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
<p>a-To evaluate the effectiveness of e-learning website to improve nurses knowledge of Del & rec. of Del.</p> <p>b- too measure nurses satisfaction for this method of learning (McCrow, Sullivan, & Beattie, 2013)</p>	<p>Pre/post cluster randomized controlled trial. Critical care, surgical, orthopedic & medical units of 3 similar size hospitals in Australia.</p> <p>IC: full-time/ part-time RNs, $n = 72$ I & 75 C.</p> <p>EC: low readiness score in self-assessment questionnaire.</p> <p>I: web-based education on Del management, recognition using CAM, subtypes of Del & link to best practice and Del management guideline. Baseline (T1) assessment on RNs before randomly grouping them.</p>	<p>RNs→ two groups: I & C (questionnaire on Del k & Del rec testing) 6-8weeks online education)</p> <p>Posttest (T2) immediately after. T3 RNs evaluated → longer term effect of education.</p> <p>Questionnaire → 27 questions, 5-point Likert scale, with good internal validity. Del k→34 questions</p> <p>Del rec measured by 5 short validated cases.</p> <p>LMM→ evaluated data. descriptive & intention -to-treat→ to evaluate</p>	<p>RN Female > male; BSN 68% $n = 100$. Baseline: Del rec scored 2.89/5(total). Del k 19.67/34.</p> <p>correct DX: 78% of dementia, 67% of hyperactive del, 58% of hyper active del superimposed dementia, hypoactive Del 50%, hypoactive superimpose dementia 37%. No statistically difference between knowledge & Dx between I & C ($p = .61$ & $p = 0.79$). ↑Knowledge T3 & T1 ($p \leq .001$). T2 & T1($p \leq .001$ DX: T2 & T1 ($t = 2.56$, $p = .011$), T3 & T1 ($p = 0.074$). In average I group had 14 % ↑Dx.</p> <p>80 % ($n = 49$) filled out questionnaires for satisfaction, 84 % liked navigation system, 78% reported website improved their knowledge, 80% found the learning flexible & relevant to clinical practice.</p>	<p>Web education had positive effect on Del Knowledge and ability to recognize Del among RNs. RNs were highly satisfied with web-based education. Potential chance to improve outcome. Not significant difference between T3 & T1 confirm the need for continuity of education. Change is possible with employing resources for education nurses.</p>

Purpose	Design/variables/sample/ setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
		impact of primary characteristic/ outcomes.		
a-Literature review related to Del unrec by RNs b-summarization of the quantitative data on unrec. Del. c- report the finding about unrec Del.(El Hussein et al., 2015).	Systemic review IC: English articles. Has quantitative research on Del age ≥ 65 , in acute care facilities. EC: conference proceeding paper, editorial, opinion, review paper 8 studies	CINAHL, MEDLINE, PsycINFO, Google Scholar	no consistency between MD & RNs in defining Del. RNs score lower to rec Del; this inconsistency can be cause of failure to identify or intervene. Education staff on CAM showed increase rec rate (agreed among studies). Rice et al. (2011): researcher rec Del in 7% of the patients while RN 75% failed to rec Del in the same group; CAM alone is not sufficient to rec del, nurse knowledge and comprehension of why they should use the CAM is important too. Lack of knowledge to rec Del, fear of performing comprehensive mental assessment are the key factors for RNs to not be able to rec Del (Eden & Forman, 1996). RNs lack of knowledge is due to minimum education on Del in nursing programs (Akechi et al., 2010). RNs have minimum knowledge of negative outcome of Del (Flagg et al, 2010).	All studies agreed on lack of knowledge is the reason for RNS unrec Del. Del rec. & identification \uparrow when nurses receive comprehensive education for using a validated screening tool. Rec Del superimpose dementia is more difficult and need a comprehensive clinical education for RNs. Rice et al. (2011) suggest that more study must be done to evaluate how RNs assess cognitive change and what is the process of their clinical decision making. This article is summarization of 8 studies more than synthesizing the finding among them
To compare the educational program between 2 hospitals: a) describe the training and impacts on	Descriptive study. Acute care hospital Gero program & CAM, B acute care non-profit w/no geriatric program or CAM. Intervention \rightarrow first to A.	Ongoing data collection & evaluation of the education program during education &	In A: posttest ($n = 21$) \rightarrow 45% \uparrow in knowledge. Confidence to apply CAM \uparrow - not statistically significant on apply or value, but on knowledge (sealing effect of the pretest).	CAM screening in both hospital improved after training. + response of staff to the training on use of CAM confirms education program has + effect on delirium perception about recognizing it. Three problems were identified during implementation: Del score

Purpose	Design/variables/sample/setting	Methods/Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
staff, b) evaluate the change pre/post and during sustainability period, c) describe the difference between 2 models, d) compare the results with data base (Filinson et al., 2016)	3.75 contact h education to A, two years later → B. a year after education, CAM training in A ($n = 29$) & B: 4 months after initial training CAM education was offered ($n = 40$). Policy→ for CAM, A: pt age ≥ 65 routing screen of Del on admission & each shift. In B: CAM conducted based on mental status change in patient, not based on advanced age.	screening phase. feedback of A was used in B planning. Information extracted from information system in 3 & 6 months after implementation. Confidence on knowledge, skill & confidence to use CAM: Likert scale (1-5) tool.	In B: post-test →↑knowledge (75%). Self eval on value and apply not significant change. but in area of knowledge, skill & confidence significantly improved both hospitals ($p < .0001$) Applying CAM↑ in A: 36.2→76 %, & in B: 0→ 67% Sustainability in Hospital B ↓from 667% → 36.7 % ($p < .001$). A: 90.8 % compliance.	misunderstood by RN, pharmacy was not notified, & RN did not completed CAM. This study highlighted the problem of Del rec on the units that are not familiar with Del, and mental screening tools. Education can reduce the resistance of assessment& help with sustainability. No explanation of initial training & number of sample, or control group in each hospital.
To evaluate Staff RN ability to DX and initiate early intervention on Del pts (Malik et al., 2016).	Descriptive study. Veteran hospital acute medical unit Tennessee. IC: medical pts, age ≥ 65 , RN staff ($n = 40$) & pts ($n = 740$). Data collection 4 months. EC; pts outside inpatient unit. Pre/post education eval on staff knowledge on Del.	Knowledge assessment Questionnaire, pre and post education. mRASS, retrospective evaluation of chart on; age, LOS, DX,	Staff knowledge: response rate ↑ pre → post (60% →85%), knowledge (58%→ 61%). mRASS utilization between 49-61 % of monthly admission. At first staff were not documenting use of supplies to manage Del.	Del screening ↑ staff awareness of Del rec and management. # of toolbox use to manage Del ↑ after educating staff, and bringing awareness Notes: Author does not explain why compliance to education was low. Not a strong study, it mainly reported on implementation of QI, with very limited data to support outcomes. Author mentioned that he was hoping for higher score of post knowledge tests and screening after education. Based on the author explanation there had been many problems with data collection: mRASS not been in electronic system, RN not documenting use of box to manage Del.

Purpose	Design/variables/sample/setting	Methods/Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
To recognize and group the barriers of low support for Del care guideline among nurses by evaluating other professions perspective to Del guideline (Steeg et al., 2014)	Qualitative study. All hospitals in Netherlands were invited & 19 accepted to participate. <i>n</i> = 63 (28 RNs, 17 hospitals' policy advisors, 18 MD). participants were selected by asking hospital to nominate them.	Open-ended semi-structured interview (30 -45 minutes). Audiotaped, in person or phone interviews. Transcripts were coded using MAXQDA 2007(thematic coding).	-lack of motivation "oh not more" RNs viewing screening as another <u>registration form</u> . - level of knowledge & skill (nurses think they have enough knowledge to rec Del and don't need to use the tool. - context and resources: the priority of screening is not as high as other tasks in their short available time -professional role and identity: nurses do not see screening essential part of elderly care. report screening is the first item they omit when they don't have enough time.	"Individual, social and organizational factors play roles in adherence of Del screening. Some barriers were obvious such as understanding pts benefits in following the guideline. 'the interplay between the context and the behavior that habituate the behavior should be considered" Nurse usually equate screening with registration not actual rec of Del. Inflexibility of guideline make it hard to follow. When introducing a new change, reasons for expected behavior change & its benefit to pt care should be clearly highlighted through education and receiving immediate feedbacks
literature review to identify educational interventions that helps with Del rec (Yanamadala et al., 2013).	Systemic literature review. Search word listed (<i>n</i> = 26) primary focus: educational intervention for Del rec& reported outcomes	Medline & CINHAI through 2012. Categorized: target group, setting & education intervention. Interventions classified based on PRECEDE model to 4 types. Kirkpatrick model was used to evaluate outcome.	Nine study type 1 (dissemination of information) →focus on rec of Del (3/9 provided geriatric content include Del. 11 type 2 (providing resources, facilitate desire change) → use education + enabling factors like screening tool, protocol, pathways to rec Del. 1 type 3 (reinforce & deconsolidate learning through feedback), 5 type 4 (multifaceted enabling and reinforcing factors with modifying the current system to incorporate the needs, example, CAM-ICU). 10 studies showed knowledge gain, 4 showed significant gain, 2 did not mentioned any gain. Type 1 & 2 →↑ knowledge & self-confidence.	Assessment tools ↑knowledge & improve practice change & Del rec. Considering complex nature of Del, type 4 interventions most successful. Use of resource or champions, feedback on performance and use of protocol examples of effective enabling and reinforcing. Resource nurse receives exclusive training. Type 4 shows ↑staff performance, Del rec, & supporting the protocol. Most type1 did not report clinical performance /outcomes. Expectation to measurable outcome changes in type 1 is ↓. Sequence sessions in type 2 shows ↑effects (usually no outcome measures). Comprehensive education & interventions →more effective for all 4 levels of Kirkpatrick outcomes.

Purpose	Design/variables/sample/ setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
			Type 3 → several workshops not revealed ↑self-confidence. Type 4: ↑ knowledge & interrater agreement (one study reported no change).	Limitation: most study did not use validated method to evaluate knowledge or outcomes. Using simulation, scripts & case studies in combination with educational theory may enhance educational sessions. Educational intervention should have approval & support of leadership. Success of educational programs directly related to leaderships belief, understanding & support. Sustaining educational programs ↑ outcomes.

Note. CAM, confusion assessment method; CAM-ICU, confusion assessment method-intensive care unit; C, control; Del, delirium, delirious; rec. recognition; EC, excluding criteria; eval, evaluate; IC, including criteria; I, intervention; K, knowledge; LMM, linear mixed modeling; MD, medical doctor; mRASS, modified Richmond Assessment Sedation Score; LOS, length of stay; RN, registered nurse; PRECEDE, predisposing, reinforcing, enabling constructs in educational diagnosis and evaluation; QI, quality improvement project. #, number; h, hour/ hours; → had, ↑, resulted; higher, greater, increase; unrec, unrecognized

APPENDIX E

TABLE OF DELIRIUM MANAGEMENT PROGRAM

Delirium Management Programs (Non-Pharmacological)

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
A guideline to prevent and treat post operation Del (2015).	Develop a Guideline Based on ROL and categorization of strength. IC: non-pharm & pharm interventions for prevent & treat Del.	a-used IOM guideline b- ROL, c-manuscript writing & revising, d-external peer review	<p>A-Educational program for staff effective (st: high, QOE: low). Program should include: Del rec, screening tools, risk factors, non-pharm& pharm approach. - Most effective: interactive, engage leadership, use peer supports & use champions. Harm of non-pharm: no harm reported, the cost of resources, cost effectiveness in many settings.</p> <p>B-Implementation of multicomponent non-pharm interventions by multidisciplinary team ↑ clinical outcomes (st: strong, QOE: moderate) -sleep enhancement (non-pharm sleep protocol, sleep hygiene), early ambulation, cognitive reorientation, physical rehab, hearing & vision device, nutrition & fluid, pain management, appropriate meds usage, harm: non but cost.</p> <p>C-Healthcare provider implementation of multicomponent intervention (St: weak, QOE; low).</p>	<p>Successful management of post op Del needs knowledge of pharm/non-pharm interventions. The recommendations allow HCP to adapt an evidence -based system to manage /prevent Del.</p> <p>Note: The survey carried by AGS on 2014 showed Del as “the most essential topic” in elderly care.</p>

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
			<p>-Identify & management: HCP must assess, use tools to DX, arrange appropriate environment, consult & manage underline cause (st: strong, QOE: low): -delay initiation → prolong Del, ↑ mortality, ↓ cog function. Harm: recommendation even up the risk of delay treatment for underlying cause(s).</p> <p>D- specialized hospital unit: insufficient evidence for or against.</p>	
Volunteers' participation in mobilizing elderly patients in hospitals (Baczynska et al., 2016)	Systemic review articles IC: hospital based medical unit studies, mobilization, age ≥ 65; volunteer assist. EC: non-English, non-acute care setting, limited to neurological studies. 24 articles → full review → 10 selected	CINAHL, AMED, Google, Cochrane, Medline. Methodology & quality of the studies were evaluated & scored (out of 27)	<p>5 studies that used HELP, scored 22/27.</p> <p>MOVE ON: 2 studies → unable to eval, no published data yet.</p> <p>Programs: HELP, Footprints walking programs & mobility in medicine → in USA, ACTIVE → 1 article → Australia, & MOVE ON → Canada.</p> <p>HE LP → use volunteers, no clear the extent of volunteer use, some struggled find enough volunteers, HELP has been evaluated in UK, unclear if it will be run by staff or volunteers (Godfery, et al., 2013). HELP program evaluated in Netherlands, and it has reported to have benefit to help pts eat, drink & walk (Strijbos et al., 2013).</p>	<p>Findings showed a lack of scientific trials that evaluate volunteer-assist mobility, inpatient medical units. The best current program is HELP.</p> <p>Note: from 24 full reviews, 12 eliminated → lack of explanations/ define protocol. Out of 10 unable to evaluate 2, and the 3 no sufficient data (overall not much data to evaluate)</p>
To evaluate the CWH program on quality, safety, &	Pre/post mixed methods process & effect eval. 2	CWH initiated → eval. Outcomes: incidence of Del,	Incident of Del = 11% ($n = 20$) before CWH & 10 % after ($n = 20$) ($p = .945$). ↓ cog → 15% before &	CWH was implemented in satisfactory level. No significant difference was found pre & post implementation.

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
efficiency hospital care (Bakker et al., 2014).	surgical & 1 medical units Dutch university hospital. IC: age \geq 70, LOS \geq 48 h of admission. initial screen: Del, fall, malnutrition, physical decline. 1 \leq risk factors \rightarrow pt is frail \rightarrow if geriatric nurse decided the benefit from CWH \rightarrow program initiated. EC: refusal, + Del, $n = 195$ pre, & 191 post	cog, ADL during hospital stay & readmit \leq 1 month. Assessment tools: MMSE, GARS, GARS-ADL. Informal care giver minimum survey & care giver burden in 3-month after DC.	12% after ($p = .431$). \downarrow ADLs \rightarrow 31% before & 34 % after ($p = .544$). No potential confounders. Improved ADL at 3 months ($p = .058$), readmission 11% \rightarrow 15% ($p = .240$), rate of burden in scale of 0-10 ($p = .049$).	The mix eval showed that the implementation of CWH is an ongoing during pre/post. Does not show any benefit. Note: CWH is combination of geriatric intervention team, volunteers & HELP
Evaluate the effect & feasibility of PPO orders (Freter, Koller, Dunbar, Macknight, & Rockwood, 2017)	Quality improvement intervention study (pragmatic single-blinded clinical trial). tertiary care hospitals, $n = 283$ Two orthopedic units, one intervention, one control. IC: age \geq 65, with hip fx, able to sign consent. EC: pathological fx, MVA, non-English, non-ambulatory, sever comorbidity (sever infection or CHF)	Compare adherence to PPO vs. routine orders. (intervention group had PPO order in chart, control only regular order). Medical records were reviewed. CAM was used to eval for Del.	Pre-op demographic eval between 2 groups had no significant difference. Pre-op Del (57.6% over all $p = .02$) prescribe post op abx intervention vs control (98.6% vs. 99.3 % $p = .58$), post op blood work (88% vs. 95%, $p = .03$), laxative (83% vs. 88% $p = .28$), catheter removal (85% vs. 46% $p < 0.001$). Acetaminophens given more in intervention (81% vs. 43% $p < .001$). Del at post op day 1 intervention vs control: (27% vs 42%) and on day 5 (7% vs. 30%). Significant difference in medication use with PPO, less narcotic	There is good adherence of PPO among staff. PPO had less Del but no significant effect on LOS. Note; in PPO order set, there is scheduled Acetaminophen, low narcotic, no abrupt start / stop of Banzo, urinary catheter removed by day 2, laxative is scheduled, post op blood work for electrolyte, urea, low dose of Haldol for sever agitation.
People who received HELP has lower rate of 30-day readmission compare to control	University based hospital in Pittsburg, retrospective a year data collection. 8 units had active HELP program 10 control. IC: HELP	Demographic data, APR-DRG, Deyo-Charlson, Elixhauser comorbidity	HELP units; more female & black, \downarrow comorbidity based on Deyo-Charlson, & Elixhauser indexes. APR-DRG similar ($p = .70$). HELP had \downarrow unadjusted readmission rate	HELP can reduce readmission by 17.2%, 100 fewer readmission. Decreasing 30-day readmission rate can be justification for cost of HELP program

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
group (Rubin et al., 2018)	established criteria, $n = 4,794$ in HELP units & $n = 2,834$ in control units. Data collected from hospital data system.	index, LOS, and 30 days post-DC mortality rate, Dc disposition.	(16.9% vs. 18.9 %, $P = .02$). HELP adjusted readmission rate was fewer but not significant ($IRR = 0.92$, 95% CI 0.81-1.04, $p = .16$). HELP Pts DC home.	Note; in discussion researchers talk about reduce rate of readmission and its effect on cost of care
Evaluate the feasibility of conducting randomized controlled study to evaluate the effectiveness of non-pharm Del prevention program in stroke unit (Rice et al., 2017)	A prospective randomized controlled trial. At a teaching hospital USA, IC: acute ischemic & intra parenchymal hemorrhagic stroke patients age ≥ 50 . EC: subdural hematoma, non-English, + aphasia, medically unstable, LOS < 48 h. $n = 134$ (divided to $n = 59$ intervention & $n = 66$ control).	2 groups. intervention received: usual stroke care & multicomponent care + daily CAM, AChB scale & ADS, MoCA Control: stroke care + daily CAM. At discharge both groups: CAM, NIHSS, MoCA, AChB & ADS	No significant different between group age, gender, race, NIH, Rankin's scale, or type of stroke. Del incident rate 8%(10/125). # of day with Del was higher among ischemic stroke (1-5 days) in the control unit. Intervention unit: the average Del days was 2 days for all three kinds of stroke.	Multicomponent Del prevention is feasible and can be delivered without interfering with stroke related care. Note: multicomponent program: volunteer based therapeutic activities, based on HELP protocol, 15 min, twice a day. No explanation about validity of the tools specially MoCA.
Summarization of the recommendation of NICE guideline on how to recognize, prevent & treat Del (Young et al., 2010)	Recommendation is based on systemic review of evidence with consideration of cost. If no article available, it is expert opinion	systematic review of prospective cohort studies, respectively to the strength of the studies & cost effectiveness	Recommendations: Assess patients with risk for Del: age ≥ 65 , cog impairment, dementia or both, current hip fx, sever sickness with deterioration risk Intervention to prevent Del: -make sure pts at risk receive care from team that know Del care -Avoid moving Pt from room to room unless necessary. Assess at risk Pt within 24 h of admission: cog impairment,	There is a need of cooperation between Del care staff, organization & health professions. -Need to "think Delirium"- Del awareness -Implement educational program to improve poor Del detection rate. -Preventing Del should be the staff culture. - Increase Pt's family involvement in care.

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
			<p>dehydration, hypoxia, immobility, infection, multi- medication, pain, poor nutrition, sensory impairment, sleep disturbance</p> <p>Quality of article: low.</p> <p>-After DX at risk, multidisciplinary trained and competent team take care of Pt (based on low quality randomization trial & moderate evidence from prognostic cohort studies)</p> <p>Indicator of Del:</p> <p>-Fluctuation of behavior within hours or days</p> <p>-at least daily assessment is needed.</p> <p>These changes may report by Pt, care giver. Changes may affect: Cognitive function, perception, physical function, social behavior</p> <p>DX: + incidence of Del: use DSMMD or CAM to confirm DX.</p> <p>In /recovery and ICU→ CAM-ICU, if distinguish between Del, dementia, Del superimposed to Dementia is difficult, treat first for Del.</p> <p>Document DX of Del</p> <p>Initial management of Pt with Del:</p> <p>-identify & treat underlying cause (low evidence)</p> <p>= initiate an effective communication</p> <p>-provide an appropriate care environment</p>	

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
			Distressed Pts: medications?	
The goal of this project is to integrate NICE guideline with HELP protocol(Yue et al., 2014)	Use IOM guide to develop a guideline	Compare NICE & HELP through comprehensive literature review, CINAHL, PubMed. IC: English article, between 2008-2012, internal peer review & external review	NICE has 3 more area of care Hypoxia, infection, & pain Since infection is broad area →focus on three items related to HELP: hand hygiene, aspiration Pneumonia prevention & CAUTI Dehydration protocol expanded to include constipation	NICE to help filled out the gap in the well-known cost-effective program, HELP
To determine feasibility of HELP model in nursing home, Program runs by CNA (Boockvar et al., 2016)	Outcome analysis Pre/post evaluation on Del. & functional capacity. Intervention: HELP- LTC implements delirium prevention activities. 11 intervention & 6 control units. Setting: 17 long care units. size: 231 IC (based on pharmacy query): Pts with acute illness, new abx, IV fluid EC: LOS < 2 months on rehab, hospice, nonverbal, unable to participate in activities, Intervention duration: symptoms + 1 week	Comparison between intervention/control. Interventions (int.): orientation, Cog/mobility activities, Hydration, snacks, sleep relaxation & medication alerts. Measures: CAM, DI, ADL, BIMS, MDS, Mean of BMIS, ADL & MDS score. post-interview Pts /staff satisfaction.	CNA delivered 15.9 ± 6.8 visit/day, average visit: 32.3 ± 13.1 min Completed Cog activities: 97%, PhF activities: 84%, fluid: 90%, snack: 76%, sleep: 86% (n = 148) Del assess. by coordinator: 6.1 ± 2.7 times post eval: mean DI score ↓ (3.9→2.3), (p = .03). between Day 0→Day 12, Mean BIMS ↑ (10.0 → 11.1) (p < .001). Mean ADL score did not change (19.6 vs 19.7; p = .94).” 27 of 28 patients were satisfied. 14 out of 17 staff endorsed the program	Program is feasible for CNAs to do the HELP interventions. Del incidence decreased with intervention. CNA increase care intensity in area that busy RN was not able to perform. This ↑ job satisfaction. Limitation: design did not measure effectiveness (no formal control group). Del severity decreased by intervention. My note: CNA education 16 h. 3 hours demonstration/ one-hour teaching. The program lead did screening based on pharmacy meds & staff documentations. Time CNA spent: 30-60 min/day/Pt. overall not a strong study, not many data presented.

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
To evaluate feasibility of replication of HELP interventions by using QI (Rubin et al., 2006).	Quality improvement. Setting: 500 bed community hospital data collection over 3.5 years on initiated HELP units. <i>n</i> = 4763 patients age >70 IV: HELP multicomponent interventions for management. DV: cost, Pt /staff satisfaction	Pre/post measure Del rate, cost of care, LOS, use of tranquilizers, restraints, Pre/post nurse /patient satisfaction (Likert-type surveys). Data collection: chart review of 200 discharge summaries.	Demographics similar before/after HELP. Del rate ↓: 40.8% to 26.4% (<i>p</i> < .002). relative reduction 35.3%. Cost ↓ by 14.4%. Total LOS ↓ by 0.3 days (<i>p</i> = .32). Satisfaction ↑: Nurses (3.8 to 4.3); Pts (2.8-3.0).	HELP decreased rates of delirium, cut costs, increased nurse/patient satisfaction. My note: modified HELP protocol, no admission or discharge functional status data was collected. Pre-data: showed Del under DX on discharge (2.5%). They used proxy to evaluate the rate. This study method can be used as a model for other hospitals. Limitation: dissemination outside the original hospitals hard, need educational campaigns. Not having control group.
To develop, test and evaluate sustainable delirium prevention program for UK (Godfrey et al., 2013)	Qualitative interview/observation (descriptive) study. “Intervention: Education sessions and workshops offered to staff and volunteers. 3 hospitals in north England, Elderly care units., ortho, ER. Data from workshop, relevant documents, one-to-one interviews, and unit observation. 31 individuals (MD, RN, therapists, specialist/managers, care givers, volunteer services	Phenomenon: knowledge & practice related to Del. & Del. prevention; -Professional & organizational factors in service delivery. NPT tool: coherence, cognitive participation, collective action & reflective monitoring. Whether staff work individually or collectively	1. Knowledge and awareness of delirium varied among staff. Lack of knowledge & training → low Coherence in NPT terms. 2. Del prevention was challenging due to low coherence; which showed lack of cog. participation in NPT. 3. Current practice: Del. prevention is not a driver of care 4. Developing Prevention program (POD)	Recommended POD program over HELP. POD is more flexible, can be built over existing structure. Evolving model combined staff practice change & enhanced volunteer roles. Staff knowledge about delirium - necessity. My Note: POD is more practical for hospital that doesn't want to change the infrastructure / add extra budget for delirium care. It emphasizes on quality improvement and nursing and volunteer education.

Purpose	Design/variables/ sample/setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
	managers/ volunteers) interviewed + 50 h observation	influence on Del. management.		
Identify challenges to implement human factor changes such as HELP (Bradley, Schlesinger, Webster, Baker, & Inouye, 2004)	Qualitative study 9 hospitals with HELP	58 Phone interviews; 32 participants Staff experiences implementing HELP/challenges & strategies to success. Constant comparative method” to analyze data /used common coding techniques	leadership (high personal commitment to program, knowledge of Org. culture), 3- Integrate with current geriatric policy, 4-Balance program fidelity with hospital circumstances (emphasize outcomes), 5-Document & publicized positive outcomes, 6- Maintain momentum (manage expectations)	Conscious effort to define & promote the program is needed. Change happens slowly; timing should be realistic/ Important of diffusing the innovation to practice

Note. abx, antibiotics; AChB, anticholinergic cognitive burden; Admin, admission; ADL, activity of daily living; ADS, anticholinergic drug scale; ACTIVE, Aged Care Therapeutic interventions by Volunteers; Asses, assessment; aged care therapeutic interventions by volunteers; APR-DRG, all-patient refined diagnosis-related group; AGS, American Geriatrics Society; cog, cognitive; BIMS, Brief Interview of Mental Status; CAM, confusion assessment method; CNA, certified nursing assistant; CWH, care well hospital program; CAUTI, catheter associated urinary tract infection; CHF, congestive heart failure; Cog, cognitive; DC, discharge; Del, Delirium, delirious; DI, delirium index; DSMMD-IV, diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorder, fourth edition; DX, diagnosis; DV, dependent variable; fx, fracture; eval, evaluate, evaluation; EC, exclusion criteria; ED, emergency department; GARS, Groningen activity restriction scale; HCP, health care providers; HELP, hospital elder life program; HELP-LTC, HELP program long term care (Nursing home); IC, inclusion criteria; ICU, intensive care unit; IOM, Institute of Medicine; IRR, incidence rate ratio for unplanned readmission; IQCODE, Informant Questionnaire on Cognitive Decline in the Elderly; IV, independent variable; IV, intravenous; LOS, length of stay; MVA, motor vehicle accident; MDS, minimum data set; Min = minutes; MMSE, mini-mental state examination; MoCA, a brief cognitive screening test. MOVE ON, mobilization of vulnerable elders in Ontario; MIS, Memory Impairment Screen; Meds, medications; NIHSS, National institute of health stroke scale; NH, nursing home; NICE, national institute for health and clinical excellence; PhF, Physical Function; POD, name of a program “Prevention of Delirium.” QOE, quality of evidence; RASS, Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale; Readmit, readmission; REMS, Rapid Emergency Medicine Score; RA, research assistant; ROL, Review of literature; Pt(s), Patient(s); pharm, pharmacological; Rec, recognition; rehab, rehabilitation; St, strength; post op, post operation; PPO, delirium prevention preprinted orders; SD, standard deviation; SNF, Skilled Nursing Facilities; UK: United Kingdom. ↓ = decrease. ↑ = increase. → = therefore. # = number. < = less /less than. > = greater

APPENDIX F

TABLE OF FRAMEWORK

Framework: KAP-O

Purpose	Design/variables/sample/ setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
To identify underlying cause that assist improve knowledge attitude, preventative practice and outcome (Rav-Marathe et al., 2016)	Systemic review of conceptual frameworks. No description on methods or sample size.	Review articles, the behavioral theory relevant to change diabetic Pt behavior.	Human health behavioral theories do not measure actual health behaviors are time consuming. KAP model develop 1950. from 1960 mainly used in family planning studies. KAP studies cost-effective, mainly used in health education for patient behavioral & outcome changes. Now, KAP widely use to address human behavior when affected by disease/problem. KAP directly related; knowledge and attitude affect practice. Surveys to evaluate each construct. Mostly non-experimental descriptive researches. It evaluates effect of change in one variable to variation of other variables.	Several categories of studies are reported. One of the category is the group of study that stated the education improve knowledge and attitude, & consequently improves practice.
To examine linear relationship between KAPs & discuss factors that explain relationship between KAP	Cross-sectional study in Uganda, community -based study	Survey questionnaires and observational checklists to find the finding related to KAP	Knowledge and attitude have more linear relationship than knowledge and practice. the correlation between knowledge & attitude is high (CI= 0.76 (.69-.81) $p = 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$) not the same for knowledge &	KAP started as scientific measurement now has been used in political persuasions. The linear relationship between KAP constructs exist. However, there is critical level of knowledge -attitude in where the linear model doesn't exist anymore.

Purpose	Design/variables/sample/ setting	Methods/ Measure	Findings	Conclusion/ Limitations & notes
construct (Muleme et al., 2017)			practice (CI= .32 (.18-.45) $p = 1.87 \times 10^{-5}$)	Implementing awareness campaign alone may not be enough for behavior change. "Smaller P value means the probability of getting the extreme case was lower."
Report on utilization of tools to measure hand hygiene compliance (Rynga et al., 2017)	Cross section study of knowledge attitude & practice. A tertiary hospital in India. $n = 75$	Self-report HCW. Closed-end structured questionnaire (from WHO survey) plus observation	56% of HCW had training, 96% reported they know 6 steps in hand hygiene, however only 47% knew the correct answer the level of compliance was 14.6%	Although mostly self-reported that they have knowledge about hand hygiene, there are gap in practice. Th environment & infrastructure need to be considered to reach to maximum practice change.

Note. KAP, knowledge, attitude, practice; HCW, health care worker; WHO, world Health Organization;

APPENDIX G

ASSESSMENT TOOLS: KATZ ADLS

Katz Index of Independence in Activities of Daily Living

Patient Name: _____ Date: _____

Patient ID # _____

Katz Index of Independence in Activities of Daily Living		
Activities Points (1 or 0)	Independence (1 Point)	Dependence (0 Points)
	NO supervision, direction or personal assistance.	WITH supervision, direction, personal assistance or total care.
BATHING Points: _____	(1 POINT) Bathes self completely or needs help in bathing only a single part of the body such as the back, genital area or disabled extremity.	(0 POINTS) Need help with bathing more than one part of the body, getting in or out of the tub or shower. Requires total bathing
DRESSING Points: _____	(1 POINT) Get clothes from closets and drawers and puts on clothes and outer garments complete with fasteners. May have help tying shoes.	(0 POINTS) Needs help with dressing self or needs to be completely dressed.
TOILETING Points: _____	(1 POINT) Goes to toilet, gets on and off, arranges clothes, cleans genital area without help.	(0 POINTS) Needs help transferring to the toilet, cleaning self or uses bedpan or commode.
TRANSFERRING Points: _____	(1 POINT) Moves in and out of bed or chair unassisted. Mechanical transfer aids are acceptable.	(0 POINTS) Needs help in moving from bed to chair or requires a complete transfer.
CONTINENCE Points: _____	(1 POINT) Exercises complete self control over urination and defecation.	(0 POINTS) Is partially or totally incontinent of bowel or bladder
FEEDING Points: _____	(1 POINT) Gets food from plate into mouth without help. Preparation of food may be done by another person.	(0 POINTS) Needs partial or total help with feeding or requires parenteral feeding.
TOTAL POINTS: _____ SCORING: 6 = High (patient independent) 0 = Low (patient very dependent)		

Source:
try this: Best Practices in Nursing Care to Older Adults, The Hartford Institute for Geriatric Nursing, New York University, College of Nursing, www.hartfordign.org.

MaineHealth

Katz ADLs. From: trythis. Best Practices in Nursing Care to Older Adults, The Hartford Institute for Geriatric Nursing, New York University, College of Nursing, www.hartfordign.org retrieved from:
<https://clas.uiowa.edu/socialwork/sites/clas.uiowa.edu.socialwork/files/NursingHomeResource/documents/Katz>

APPENDIX H

CHARLSON COMORBIDITY INDEX

Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI) Calculator

This Charlson comorbidity index calculator assesses the 10 year survival/mortality risk in patients with several comorbidities based on the CCI scoring system. Discover the conditions and their weights in the model and how the outcome probability is calculated below the form.

<input type="checkbox"/> Patient Age:*	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Myocardial Infarction	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Congestive Heart Failure	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Peripheral Vascular Disease	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Cerebrovascular Disease	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Dementia	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> COPD	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Connective Tissue Disease	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Peptic Ulcer Disease	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Diabetes Mellitus	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate to severe Chronic Kidney Disease	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Hemiplegia	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Leukemia	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Malignant Lymphoma	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Solid Tumor	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Liver Disease	<input type="text" value="Select"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> AIDS	<input type="text" value="Select"/>

Charlson Comorbidity Index for chart review. Charlson, M., & Foley, W. (n.d). Charlson Comorbidity Index. Retrieved 4/21/18 <http://www.bgs.org.uk/pdfs/assessment/cci.pdf>

APPENDIX I

CAM-ICU

CAM-ICU

Confusion Assessment Method for Intensive Care Unit. Boehm, L., Pun, B., & Stollings, J. (2016, August 31, 2016). Confusion assessment method for the ICU (CAM-ICU), The complete training manual. Retrieved from <http://www.icudelirium.org/resources.html>

APPENDIX J

THE RICHMOND AGITATION SEDATION SCALE (RASS)

Assessing Consciousness: Linking Level of Consciousness Monitoring

Step 1 Level of Consciousness: RASS*

Scale	Label	Description
+4	COMBATIVE	Combative, violent, immediate danger to
+3	VERY AGITATED	Pulls to remove tubes or catheters; aggr
+2	AGITATED	Frequent non-purposeful movement, fig
+1	RESTLESS	Anxious, apprehensive, movements not
0	ALERT & CALM	Spontaneously pays attention to caregiv
-1	DROWSY	Not fully alert, but has sustained awake
-2	LIGHT SEDATION	Briefly awakens to voice (eyes open & c
-3	MODERATE SEDATION	Movement or eye opening to voice (no e
If RASS is ≥ -3 proceed to CAM-ICU (Is patient CAM-ICU positive)		
-4	DEEP SEDATION	No response to voice, but movement or
-5	UNAROUSABLE	No response to voice or physical stimu
If RASS is -4 or -5 \rightarrow STOP (patient unconscious), RECHECK I		

³Sessler, et al. AJRCCM 2002; 166:1338-1344.

⁴Ely, et al. JAMA 2003; 289:2983-2991.

*For RASS equivalents to other sedation-agitation scales see FAQs page 20-21.

The Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale (RASS). Boehm, L., Pun, B., & Stollings, J. (2016, August 31, 2016). Confusion assessment method for the ICU (CAM-ICU), The complete training manual. Retrieved from <http://www.icudelirium.org/resources.html>

APPENDIX K

ASSESSMENT OF CONSCIOUSNESS: LINKING LEVEL OF CONSCIOUSNESS WITH DELIRIUM MONITORING

Assessing Consciousness: Linking Level of Consciousness & Delirium Monitoring

Step 1 Level of Consciousness: RASS*

Scale	Label	Description	
+4	COMBATIVE	Combative, violent, immediate danger to staff	VOICE
+3	VERY AGITATED	Pulls to remove tubes or catheters; aggressive	
+2	AGITATED	Frequent non-purposeful movement, fights ventilator	
+1	RESTLESS	Anxious, apprehensive, movements not aggressive	
0	ALERT & CALM	Spontaneously pays attention to caregiver	
-1	DROWSY	Not fully alert, but has sustained awakening to voice (eye opening & contact >10 sec)	
-2	LIGHT SEDATION	Briefly awakens to voice (eyes open & contact <10 sec)	
-3	MODERATE SEDATION	Movement or eye opening to voice (no eye contact)	TOUCH
If RASS is ≥ -3 proceed to CAM-ICU (Is patient CAM-ICU positive or negative?)			
-4	DEEP SEDATION	No response to voice, but movement or eye opening to physical stimulation	
-5	UNAROUSABLE	No response to voice or physical stimulation	
If RASS is -4 or -5 → STOP (patient unconscious), RECHECK later			

³Sessler, et al. AJRCM 2002; 166:1338-1344.

⁴Ely, et al. JAMA 2003; 289:2983-2991.

*For RASS equivalents to other sedation-agitation scales see FAQs page 20-21.

Step 2 Content of Consciousness: CAM-ICU

⁵Inouye, et al. Ann Intern Med 1990; 113:941-948.

⁷Ely, et al. CCM 2001; 29:1370-1379.

⁸Ely, et al. JAMA 2001; 286:2703-2710.

[Assessment of Consciousness: Linking Level of Consciousness with Delirium Monitoring](http://www.icudelirium.org/resources.html). Boehm, L., Pun, B., & Stollings, J. (2016, August 31, 2016). Confusion assessment method for the ICU (CAM-ICU), The complete training manual. Retrieved from <http://www.icudelirium.org/resources.html>

APPENDIX L

CAM-ICU WORKSHEET

CAM-ICU Worksheet		
Feature 1: Acute Onset or Fluctuating Course	Score	Check here if Present
Is the patient different than his/her baseline mental status? OR Has the patient had any fluctuation in mental status in the past 24 hours as evidenced by fluctuation on a sedation/level of consciousness scale (i.e., RASS/SAS), GCS, or previous delirium assessment?	Either question Yes →	<input type="checkbox"/>
Feature 2: Inattention		
Letters Attention Test (See training manual for alternate Pictures)		
Directions: Say to the patient, "I am going to read you a series of 10 letters. Whenever you hear the letter 'A,' indicate by squeezing my hand." Read letters from the following letter list in a normal tone 3 seconds apart. SAVEAHAART or CASABLANCA or ABADBADAAY Errors are counted when patient fails to squeeze on the letter "A" and when the patient squeezes on any letter other than "A."	Number of Errors >2 →	<input type="checkbox"/>
Feature 3: Altered Level of Consciousness		
Present if the Actual RASS score is anything other than alert and calm (zero)	RASS anything other than zero →	<input type="checkbox"/>
Feature 4: Disorganized Thinking		
Yes/No Questions (See training manual for alternate set of questions)		
1. Will a stone float on water? 2. Are there fish in the sea? 3. Does one pound weigh more than two pounds? 4. Can you use a hammer to pound a nail? Errors are counted when the patient incorrectly answers a question. Command Say to patient: "Hold up this many fingers" (Hold 2 fingers in front of patient) "Now do the same thing with the other hand" (Do not repeat number of fingers) *If the patient is unable to move both arms, for 2 nd part of command ask patient to "Add one more finger" An error is counted if patient is unable to complete the entire command.	Combined number of errors >1 →	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall CAM-ICU		<input type="checkbox"/>
Feature 1 <u>plus</u> 2 <u>and</u> either 3 <u>or</u> 4 present = CAM-ICU positive		<input type="checkbox"/> CAM-ICU Positive (Delirium Present)
		<input type="checkbox"/>
		<input type="checkbox"/> CAM-ICU Negative (No Delirium)

Confusion Assessment Method for Intensive Care Unit (CAM-ICU) worksheet. Boehm, L., Pun, B., & Stollings, J. (2016, August 31, 2016). Confusion assessment method for the ICU (CAM-ICU), The complete training manual. Retrieved from <http://www.icudelirium.org/resources.html>

APPENDIX M

HOSPITAL CONFIRMATION LETTER

A m

Date: April 26, 2018
To: Ruhi Linda Mahjoub
From: Diane Drake, PhD, RN Chair Nursing Research Council and
Linda Standiford, MBA, RN Director Clinical Excellence
Re: California State University Fullerton, DNP study at Mission Hospital

Dear Ms. Mahjoub (Ruhi),

We are pleased you are in preparation of your study proposal in the DNP program to do your study at Mission Hospital. We look forward to reviewing the proposal with the Nursing Research Council.

Nursing Research Council meets the fourth Thursday of every other month. A meeting will be scheduled to accommodate your school and work schedule.

During your proposal preparation, we would be glad to meet with you to discuss the details of conducting the study at Mission. Your pursuit of scholarly work and we are glad you have decided to conduct your study at your home hospital, Mission Hospital.

At the best,

Diane Drake (on phone app)
Diane Drake
Linda Standiford
Linda Standiford

27700 Medical Center Road • Mission Viejo, CA 92691
T: (949) 364-1400

A Ministry founded by the Sisters of St. Joseph of Orange

APPENDIX N

CERTIFICATION OF ST JOSEPH IRB DETERMINATION

CERTIFICATE OF IRB DETERMINATION

September 5, 2018

SJH Reference # 18-085

Protocol Title: Incidence of Delirium and Its Sequelae in Hospitalized Older Adult from Emergency Department to Medical Surgical Units

Dear Ms. Linda Mahjoub:

This is to advise you that the St. Joseph Health Institutional Review Board reviewed your submission through the Expedited Review procedure and took the following action:

IRB Action: Approved: 09/03/2018**Submission Details:** Consent form revised to address requirements of the CSU IRB. Addition of co-investigator and change to role of study personnel.**Action Explanation:** The information does not alter the risk/benefit assessment of the study. The submission is approved. Patricia Ayala is approved as a co-investigator.The following documents were reviewed:

- Amendment to Previously Approved Research
- Application for Expedited Review final v. 7.7.18
- 18-085 Informed Consent dated 8-17-18
- 18-085 Informed Consent Showing Tracked Changes
- CV - Ayala, Patricia
- Study protocol received 7-23-18

Note: This submission involves minor changes to previously approved research, and does not increase the risk level of the study. The full IRB will be informed of the above noted submission and action in the convened St. Joseph Health IRB #2 meeting on: September 18, 2018.

St. Joseph Health, Center for Clinical Research
2342 McAdams Drive, Suite 100 Irvine, CA 92612 (949) 332-4907
FW:400620092; SORCS00740; IRB00000928 (SJH IRB #1); IRB00000928 (SJH IRB #2)
This approval verifies the IRB operates in accordance with applicable ICH, federal, state, local and institutional regulations, and with all GCP guidelines governing institutional IRB operations.

APPENDIX O

INFORMED CONSENT FORM/ PATIENT'S BILL OF RIGHT

EXPERIMENTAL SUBJECT'S BILL OF RIGHTS

Any person who is requested to consent to participate as a subject in a research study involving a medical experiment, or who is requested to consent on behalf of another, has the right to:

1. Be informed of the nature and purpose of the experiment.
2. Be given an explanation of the procedures to be followed in the medical experiment, and any drug or device to be used.
3. Be given a description of any attendant discomforts and risks reasonably to be expected from the experiment.
4. Be given an explanation of any benefits to the subject reasonably to be expected from the experiment, if applicable.
5. Be given a disclosure of any appropriate alternative procedures, drugs, or devices that might be advantageous to the subject, and their relative risks and benefits.
6. Be informed of the avenues of medical treatment, if any, available to the subject after the experiment if complications should arise.
7. Be given an opportunity to ask any questions concerning the experiment or the procedures involved.
8. Be instructed that consent to participate in the medical experiment may be withdrawn at any time, and the subject may discontinue participation in the medical experiment without prejudice.
9. Be given a copy of a signed and dated written consent form when one is required.
10. Be given the opportunity to decide to consent or not to consent to a medical experiment without the intervention of any element of force, fraud, deceit, duress, coercion, or undue influence on the subject's decision.

Study Title: Incidence of Delirium and Its Sequelae in Older Adults Entering the Hospital from Emergency Department to Non-ICU Units

Protocol Number: St. Joseph Health: 18-085; California State University Fullerton: HSR-18-19-49

Researchers:

Linda Mahjoub Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) student at California State University Fullerton (Principal Investigator)

Dr. Dana N. Rutledge, RN, PhD. Professor Emeritus, Nursing, California State University Fullerton (Co-investigator)

Dr. Roxanne O'Brien RN, PHD. Professor, Nursing, California State University Fullerton (Advisor)

Site Location: Mission Hospital, Mission Viejo CA

You are being asked to take part in a research study carried out by **Linda Ruhi Mahjoub and Dr. Rutledge under advisory of Dr. O'Brien, Faculty of California State University, School of Nursing**. This consent form explains the research study and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Before you decide, you may want to discuss the information in this document with your friends, family, or other physicians who take care of you. Ask the principal investigator (Linda Mahjoub) to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

The purpose of this study is to find out how often older persons entering the hospital from the emergency room become delirious during their hospital stay. Delirium is an acute state of confusion and altered attention that has been found in some hospitalized patients. Another aim of this study is to determine whether the incidence of delirium influences the length of hospital stays, function at the time of discharge, and discharge destination. The findings of this study will help us to consider adopting a delirium prevention and management program.

You are being asked to take part because you are 65 years and older and admitted to a non-ICU unit in the hospital.

Taking part in the study will take **about 5 minutes each day** for a total of three days. You cannot take part in this study if you are not 65 years and older, you are listed to be admitted to ICU unit, you do not speak English, or you have a history of dementia or history of antipsychotics/narcotics medications use, or you have alcohol intoxication.

How many participants will take part in the study?

Up to 300 participants will take part.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you agree to participate in this study, you will sign this consent form. The investigator will review your medical record for information about your past medical history, age and living condition (live at home or nursing home). At a convenient time, **every day for 3 days from your admission**, the investigator will assess your attention by asking to state the months of the year backward. This test takes less than a minute to complete. If you are unable to state the months backward, the investigator will screen you for delirium by asking you a few questions. The delirium screening takes less than 3 minutes to perform. Each day, the investigator will evaluate your function level which involves things like can you bathe or feed yourself. The investigator's assessments may take about 5 minutes each day. The screenings are not part of routine care but do not interfere with the treatment you receive in the hospital. Once you are discharged, the investigator will also collect information about how long you were in the hospital, whether you had a fall, or required restraints or a sitter for your care.

How long will I be in the study?

You will be visited by the investigator for three days while in the hospital. However, once you are discharged, your medical record will be reviewed to finalize, and get the final information needed for the study.

What is my responsibility?

It is important that you follow your study investigator's instructions throughout the study. If you have any questions or need further information, contact your study investigator.

Can I stop being in the study?

You can decide to withdraw from the study at any time. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. Please inform your study investigator if you are thinking about withdrawing or decide to withdraw. This decision will not affect your current or future care by your doctors or the hospital.

The study investigator may stop you from taking part in this study at any time if it is in your best interest. Visits by the study investigator will stop if you transfer to Intensive Care Unit.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

Taking part in this study does not have any direct effect on your care. We do know that the information from this study will help the investigator learn more about the incidence of delirium and its outcomes among hospitalized older adults. This information could help us to develop a prevention and management plan for future patients.

This study does not involve any treatment beyond those you have come to the hospital to receive. The investigator will assess your attention and function level three times and document those. This information should not influence your medical diagnosis and treatment you will receive during your hospital stay.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

Because this study is nonexperimental, the risk should be minimal. There is no direct risk for participation, other than potential disturbance of your comfort. However, the investigator will try not to disturb you if you are sleeping, eating, having visitors, or having pain. In addition, there may be unknown risks, or risks that we did not anticipate. For more information about potential risks with participating in this study, talk to your study investigator.

What happens if I am injured because I took part in this study?

Injury should not result from participation in this study because participation does not require taking any additional medicines, changing your current or future treatments, or undergoing any additional procedures. If you think that you may have been injured by participating in this research study, tell your study investigator as soon as you can.

Financial compensation for such things as lost wages, disability, or discomfort due to any research-related injury is not available, but you do not give up any legal rights by signing this form.

If I choose to not take part in this study, what other alternatives or choices do I have?

Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. Your choice for not taking part in this study will not affect your plan of care and medical care at the hospital.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

The data for this study will be kept confidential to the extent allowed by law. No published results will identify you, and your name will not be associated with the findings. Under certain circumstances, information that identifies you may be released for internal and external reviews of this project.

We do not use your identification information in our data. Your name, medical record and any other identifying information will be kept separate from your assigned code number; all study forms will be kept safe in a locked and secure cabinet. All computerized data will be housed in secure files (password-protected) at the hospital. However, for any study, there may be the potential for loss of confidentiality based on unexpected conditions.

Your investigator may share information about you (which does not include identifying characteristics that links the data to you) with her instructors at the California State University Fullerton. She may also share study findings with the hospital nursing research advisory team and the hospital nurse researcher.

We will follow the appropriate federal laws that say we must keep your study records private and confidential. We will protect your privacy by locking the data entry computer with a security code and keeping the signed informed consents forms in a locked cabinet at the hospital.

However, we cannot guarantee total privacy and confidentiality. Your personal information may be given out as required by law. Certain people may need to see your study records, and these people must also keep the records confidential. The people who may also see your information are:

- California State University Fullerton Institutional Review Board, a committee whose purpose is to protect the safety and welfare of research subjects.
- St. Joseph Health Institutional Review Board, a committee whose purpose is to protect the safety and welfare of research subjects.
- The Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS) and the Office of Human Research Protection (OHRP) that are involved in keeping research safe for people.

The results of this study may be published or presented at professional meetings, but the identities of all research participants will remain anonymous

The data for this study will be kept for 3 years after completion of the study as it is required by CSUF.

The finding of this study will be shared with hospital administration for future planning. The findings of this study will also be published as a requirement of doctoral education at California State University Fullerton.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

Participation in this study has no cost for you; and you will not receive payment for participation.

Does the study staff receive payment for doing this study?

The investigator will not receive a payment or an increase in salary for conducting this study. This study is a project for the Doctor of Nursing Project degree, and it will be conducted by the primary investigator as a requirement for her doctoral degree.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher, Linda Mahjoub: linda.mahjoub@stjoe.org, 949-293-9421. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, you may contact the St. Joseph Health Human Research Protection Program (HRPP) Office at 949-381-4907, by mail at 3345 Michelson Drive, Suite 100, Irvine, CA 92612, by email at HRPP@stjoe.org, or via the Internet at www.stjoe.org/Research. You may also contact the California State University Fullerton Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719, or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time. No matter what decision you make, there will be no penalty to you and you will not lose any of your health care benefits. Leaving the study will not affect your medical care.

By signing this form, you do not lose any of your legal rights to seek payment in case of injury resulting from this study.